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Summary

This report aims at providing a comprehensive overview of the Altmetrics scholarly landscape, its intellectual origins (chapter 3), terminologies and concepts (chapter 4), its infrastructures, measures, and relevant topics for communicating, disseminating, and assessing research (chapters 5, 6, and 7 respectively).

The report is based on a methodology that combines different channels of data collection by means of bibliometric analyses and mentions in the microblogging service Twitter, which is described in chapter 2. This procedure allowed for covering not only the most relevant but also the most recent literature on Altmetrics. Taken together, the corpus of literature discussed in this report consists of a total of 433 articles. The results show that the biggest share (82%) of articles has been published shortly after 2010, when the term has been coined. However, we also observe a relevant corpus literature that emerged around the year 2005. We argue that both of these literatures need to be analyzed in order to understand the conceptual fundament and debates of Altmetrics.

Consequently, in chapter 3, an analysis of the literature that led to the establishment of Altmetrics is provided. These first conceptualizations and reflections, we argue, structured the way new metrics of social media use in the scholarly landscape have been taken up. In the following chapter (chapter 4), we hence want to shift the focus away from the general developments in cybermetrics and webometrics towards this new and specific form of web-based scholarly communication and evaluation that emerged during the years between 2009 and 2012. Many arguments and conceptual differentiations in cybermetrics and webometrics later re-emerged in debates about these new phenomena known by 'Altmetrics'.

Chapters 5 and 6 provide an extensive overview of these phenomena in the landmark years between 2009 and 2012. In these chapters, central terminologies, infrastructures, and concepts which emerged in the years between 2009 and 2012. The analysis shows that it is still unclear how Altmetrics is understood. Consequently, Altmetrics is not one, but many terms. Given its heterogeneity, the Altmetrics narrative has flourished among different policy and scientific communities, among which bibliometrics, information science, science communication, and library science are most important. Central to the establishment of Altmetrics are Altmetrics aggregators which influence the channels for dissemination in Altmetrics (Franzen 2015) of which PloS ALM, PlumAnalytics, Altmetric.com, Impactstory are the most important. Often they provide an application programmable interface (API) through which data collected by the platform can be publicly accessed. However, they differ as to how they cover data sources and provide tools for visualization. Up to now, there is only limited understanding of how these data sources and their use by aggregators can be categorized. In this report, we argue that the way how the channels of dissemination are chosen by the scientists, collected by aggregators, and received by a scholarly and non-scholarly community can be interpreted as acts of valuation. In this way, scholarly literature about the different data sources such as social network sites, social media and video, recommending and bookmarking, and research data is discussed. The results of the literature show that research about altmetric providers and data sources are an increasingly fast developing field of investigation. Most studies deal with these data sources for scrutinization and validation issues, comparing for instance to what extent social media use is correlated to citations.

Taking stock of these central terminologies and concepts, chapter 7 covers the most recent issues that came up during the last two years (2015-2016). The chapter shows that scrutinization topics are still important, however, there are new issues that take a more reflexive stance towards the establishment of Altmetrics in the scientometric and informetric context. Increasingly, studies focus on the motivations and interests of users. These perspectives are also put forward by pleas for content analyses of different sources. Such knowledge is important in order to understand how different channels of dissemination are to be understood from a sociology of valuation perspective. Also, the frequently reported result that Altmetrics measures show only low correlations to citations should be taken as a starting point for a different issue towards Altmetrics, that is, a focus on the narratives they provide over research objects in a wider debate where boundaries between scholarly and non-scholarly communication are blurred.

Based upon the presentation of the state of the art literature, data sources and concepts, chapter 8 provides a comprehensive analysis of strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats in Altmetrics. Based on the desk research in this report we find the following issues. The list will be validated and extended in the course of the next steps in WP5.

Strengths

- Timeliness of some metrics
- Complementary information filters
- Catalyst function towards downstream impacts
- Responsiveness through open concept
- Balanced signaling of importance and impact
- Promotion of unique IDs

Weaknesses

- Data Integrity & Quality
- Confusion through Composite Indicators
- Conceptual and terminological confusion
- Gaming
- Lack of research into Altmetrics on data, software and video content

Opportunities

- New theoretical perspectives on impact
- New ways of understanding the dynamics of science
- Potential for new cultures of appreciation
- Increased Speed up knowledge turnover
- New ways of engaging and improving as a researcher
- Motivations for improving data access and quality

Threats

- Algorithmization of reception and knowledge flows
- Strong dependence of Altmetrics on Digital Object Identifiers

1. Introduction

The term 'Altmetrics' has in the recent years become an increasingly relevant concept both in the context of scientific and scholarly communication as well as in the realm of evaluation. The establishments of new scientific topics such as Altmetrics can generate a substantial amount of turmoil on a conceptual basis but also in terms of the clash of established and new paradigmatic interpretations of what appears to be relevant. Such irritations can lead to bargaining about the nature and relevance of a scientific field, its central terms and concepts and the legitimacy of its questions (Elias et al. 1982; Frickel and Gross 2005), which in turn eventually lead to review and state-of-the-art articles establishing an order within the corpus of the literature amassed up to a specific point in time (Bastide et al. 1989).

Altmetrics are no exception to this phenomenon. In 2012, two years after the term Altmetrics was coined and one year after the now dominant Altmetrics providers and aggregators have been founded, Wouters & Costas (Wouters and Costas 2012) produced a first comprehensive overview of the landscape of Altmetrics at that time, focusing on new forms of measurement from a functional and provider-based perspective. Closely related to Altmetrics, yet taking an overall broader stance on the topic of evaluation, the EC-funded ACUMEN project (Academic Careers Understood through Measurements and Norms) conducted a study on web-based indicators (Kousha and Thelwall 2015b, Thelwall and Kousha 2015b, 2015d).

Most recently, during the compilation of this report, three further review papers have been, or are in the process of being, published (Erdt et al. 2016; Gonzalez-Valiente et al. 2016; Sugimoto et al. forthcoming) that combine most of the relevant literature which is currently available in the context of Altmetrics. Erdt et al. (2016) provided a thorough meta-analysis of 172 articles, focusing mainly on the utilization of Altmetrics for research evaluation and related topics as point of departure from which central future issues are derived. Sugimoto et al. (forthcoming) address a broader spectrum of literature with more than double the amount of articles considered, 404 Articles in total and with a wider focus that also includes social and new media use within academia in general and an overview of factors influencing social media use of scholars, stakeholders and user groups. Furthermore, the article deals with relevant potentials and limitations in Altmetrics towards the construction, interpretation, and use of social media for evaluation purposes. González-Valiente et al. (2016) took a different approach, covering 253 articles. Yet their review was more aimed at assessing the evolution and structure of the field for the period of 2005-2015 by analyzing and visualizing the co-authorship networks. Such attempts, especially the three most recent, excellent contributions, cannot be ignored. Therefore, this report will focus on considering issues not or only partially addressed in these state-of-the-art observations and should be understood as a complementary effort with a specific appraisal towards the overall goal of OpenUp, namely to establish support of all relevant stakeholders from a holistic perspective of a 'review-disseminate-assess' cycle. This focus includes the assessment of major intellectual origins that led to the establishment of Altmetrics and the issues that have been discussed in these endeavours. We also argue that some of the conceptual and terminological confusion which shape the current debate can be traced back to a lack of theoretical conceptualizations but also a lack of practice oriented guidelines. This lack of conceptual grounding appears to be the main reason why scholarly attempts to assess the development of Altmetrics have not yet reached a deeper understanding of the value-entrenched latent concepts and materializations that Altmetrics provides to scholarly communication and its audiences. Only very recently, Haustein et al. (2016) presented a first attempt to these questions, relating Altmetrics to dominant and contradictory positions towards theories of citation.

This report will be a first step towards the reason for a practical and stakeholder-driven assessment by focusing on the Sociology of Valuation and Evaluation (Lamont 2012) and the Sociology of Quantification (Espeland and Stevens 2008). The choice of this perspective differs from more generalized, methodological or technical perspectives on the issue of Altmetrics as it provides one of the ways of integrating the three perspectives of OpenUp, namely peer review (WP3) as practices of valuation and evaluation, channels of dissemination (WP4) as the infrastructure and categorization of new forms of legitimate and valuable scientific output, and quantitative indicators (WP5) as

institutionalized practices that sustain or establish new hierarchies within the scientific community but also towards how notions of value co-evolve with the reception of society at large.

The report is structured as follows. In the next section (chapter 2), we provide an overview of how data and research information for this report have been collected. Social media data sources have played a crucial role in this respect. Subsequently (chapter 3), the intellectual and conceptual prehistory of Altmetrics is traced. In chapters four and five, we provide an overview of the emerging landscape Altmetrics, its actors, data sources, and the scholarly literature on these issues, taking stock of three most recent reviews in the field. We provide a deeper insight into the most recent issues of the scholarly literature that emerged in the years 2015 and 2016 since the publication output on Altmetrics increased dramatically in these years and has not been covered by the aforementioned reviews (chapter 6 & 7). Based upon these literatures and emerging issues, chapter 8 seeks to derive major strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats (SWOT) of Altmetrics and its data sources in a most comprehensive manner.

2. Methodological Approach and Data

In order to cover all relevant literature on Altmetrics, we employed a multi-method approach integrating different ways of data collection by means of bibliometric analyses and mentions in the microblogging service Twitter.

First, we employed a traditional bibliometric analysis of the literature bases on the Science Citation Index Expanded (SCIE), the Social Science Citation Index (SSCI), the Conference Proceedings Citation Index (CPCI) and the Arts & Humanities Citation Index (AHCI), as well as Scopus searching for the terms “altmetric*”, “Article Level Metric”, “ALM AND metr* or measur* or eval*”. Using this initial query, we generated a set of results and then analyzed the keywords of these articles as well as frequent n-grams within the abstracts and titles of these papers. Frequent terms and newly discovered keywords were subsequently introduced in the search query and the marginal results were assessed regarding the relevance of the newly found results. In total, we applied this procedure three times to the material in order to further optimize the results. The resulting query was used to identify a set of relevant records. This approach led to a set of 188 records for the Web of Science databases and a set of 287 records in SCOPUS. Results were checked for overlap, arriving at a total of 382 records. For the corpus of 188 records listed in WoS we generated a Citation Report for the WoS-based publications to uncover the number of citations to these articles. In total, we found that 371 articles had cited the identified 188 articles. Removing the overlap of intra-corpora citation between our initial set and the citation set, we identified 416 articles. All three corpora were then merged and duplicates were removed.

In a next step we analyzed the reference lists of these articles to uncover interesting articles that are not part of our merged corpus. In this approach we focused our analysis on such articles that are directly related to the topic of Altmetrics, namely publications that relate to such topics as webometrics or cybermetrics. These papers were qualitatively screened for such papers that already imply the upcoming Altmetrics era. Through this approach we could also identify such papers that can be argued to capture the intellectual heritage that authors found relevant to the discussion about Altmetrics.

Second, to account for the most recent developments within the field of Altmetrics we set up a technical infrastructure that tracked the terms “altmetric OR Altmetrics” for the microblogging service Twitter, starting data collection on May 18, 2016 and capturing a total of 23678 tweets (September 19, 2016). As URLs embedded in these tweets are shortened by the Twitter API to “https://t.co...”-URLS, we produced a script to unshorten all the links. In the case URLs were priorily reported as shortened links through other services we deep-unshortened the links up to 4 levels of URL shortening services. In total, we tracked 24378 events of URLs being posted via twitter messages. Accounting for duplicate and multiple mentions of URLs, we came up with 1586 unique URLs. These URLs were then screened manually and assessed, if they provided any new articles. Using this approach, we could identify 17 articles of which 8 were directly relevant to Altmetrics. Among the articles captured were also the three very recent review papers by Erdt et al. (2016), Sugimoto et al. (forthcoming) and González-Valiente (2016) relevant to the scope of this report. Especially the identification of these three very recent articles - which have not been covered by applying the more traditional bibliometric methods - shows a

particular advantage of the utilization of Altmetrics in explorative scientometric studies, that is, the timeliness of analysis.

Combining both approaches, we arrive at a corpus that covers both the most recent developments in Altmetrics and extends on the most recent literature reviews as well as accounts for a selected number of publications that can be seen as the intellectual pre-decessors of Altmetrics. In total 479 articles could be identified, which were then screened manually and assessed for inclusion in this report.

The results show that despite the recent uptake in publications related to Altmetrics after the term was coined in 2010, we can also identify some publications that are part of an uptake phase between 2005 and 2010 covering 69 articles as well as some papers that date back to the early 1990s with a total of 22 articles between 1991 and 2004 (see also Figure 1). After 2010, we observe a surge in output of articles, which cover approx. 82% of all articles related to Altmetrics. As the year 2016 is not completed yet, we applied a very conservative estimate to account for the potential output for the current year. Yet, depending on the method of forecasting, this volume could be up to 32% higher.

Figure 1: Publication Years of peer-reviewed Articles related to the topic ‘Altmetrics’

Source: SCI-E, SSCI, CPCI, AHCI, OpenUp Twitter Harvester. Estimated values for 2016.

3. The road towards Altmetrics

To understand the current situation of Altmetrics, it is beneficial to understand how and where ideas originated and which opportunities and challenges for further development may eventually emerge in the near future. With the advent of the web and the establishment of web based services, it comes as no surprise that the informetric community took up the idea of the web as a relevant new source of information flows, which will also have a relevance to scientific communication. In the following, we want to depict the road that led to the establishment and evolution of what may be best described as web-based information science. We do not attempt to focus on specific applications of these types of approaches.¹ Rather, we focus on the conceptual work that was involved in the evolution of the field. It should be noted, that bibliometrics and scientometrics had been established as a consolidated field of research at that time, with core journals such as the *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology* (founded in 1950) and the more inter-disciplinary *Scientometrics* (founded in 1979) being in place for a substantial amount of time.

3.1. Early web-based quantifications – Questions towards structure and impact of the World Wide Web on Science in the 1990s

The emergence of the web and the reception by the information science community came with a substantial amount of terminological attempts to label information science based metrics for web-based communication and interaction with the earliest candidate “Netometrics” (Bossy 1995). Bossy (1995) heralded web-based indicators as early as 1995 to be “The new face of Scientometrics”, building her assessment on the ideas by the French science studies scholars Latour and Callon arguing, that “remote files retrieval counts” or “clients hypertext links” may give way to new forms of evaluation as they represent discourse that is closer to the laboratory and a Latourian “Science in Action” perspective (Latour and Woolgar 1987). Conceptual scrutinization became a matter of urgency: “[W]e will have to decide what counts can be used as indicators (“of what?”)”, (Bossy 1995). In parallel attempts were made to establish a parallel infrastructure to the Science Citation Index but aimed at the web, dubbed the Open Text Index (Bray 1996). Ideas of a reminiscent of a global brain revolutionizing scholarly information flows and cooperation were introduced under the term “Webometry” (Abraham 1996). In parallel, Almid & Ingwersen (1996) coined the phrase “Internetometrics” in a conference paper, which they rephrased to “Webometrics” just one year for their journal publication (Almid and Ingwersen 1996). A journal termed “Cybermetrics” (1997) was founded. In the first issue of this *Journal Citations in the web* became “Sitations” (Rousseau 1997).

With these new opportunities also scrutinization of measuring the web and measuring with the web became an immediate and pressing topic (Bar-Ilan 1999; Ingwersen 1998; Snyder and Rosenbaum 1999). Also, the quality of web indexing services came into question (Clarke and Willett 1997). The usefulness of the functional capabilities of indexing services was deemed to be inadequate for bibliometric types of analyses (Lawrence & Giles, 1998). “Polymorphous mentioning” (Cronin et al. 1998), i.e. mentioning and invocation of an individual in multiple contexts was deemed to become a defining feature of Web-based scholarly communication to capture “multiple modalities of signalling behaviour which the Web affords” (Cronin et al. 1998). They also argued that web-based scholarly communication was not limited to scholarly discourse and formal communication, but also reflected informal communication among researchers. Attempts were made to enrol and adapt evaluative concepts from the realm of bibliometrics such as the Journal Impact Factor (JIF) in terms of a Web Impact Factor (WIF) (Ingwersen 1998). Same accounts for the concepts of explorative bibliometrics, such as bibliographic coupling and co-citation for the web (Kleinberg 1999).

¹ In a similar vein, Benoit Godin (2006) has provided a conceptual history of bibliometrics, focusing on the establishments that paved the way to its institutionalization, Godin (2006).

3.2. Reflection and Consolidation in web metrics and cybermetrics 2000-2008

Beginning with the year 2000, informetrics entered a phase of further scrutinization and conceptual reflection. This period also featured a surge in “correlation studies”, which aimed at assessing statistical correlations between established bibliometric and webometric indicators and concepts.² Such studies have merits in their own right, especially in cases in which correlations are positive and significant. These cases, it can be argued, can contribute understanding the relationship between bibliometric and cybermetric concepts and thereby shift the discussion about such indicators to the remaining advantages or disadvantages for each metric. If no such correlation or low levels of correlation are found, discourse shifts either towards further methodological scrutinizations and inclusion of further variables (or properties thereof) or towards arguments that such indicators may measure a different form of impact, which in turn can be a subject of subsequent debate.

Concentrating on the main issues of this report, we will not go into the details towards these types of studies, which should not negate their importance in development of the field. Rather, we want to shed light on publications that focused on conceptual papers about the expected impacts of new web-based forms of scholarly communication and their reception and uptake in the cybermetric/webometric community. Harter & Ford (2000) were the first to highlight systematic issues and challenges for web-based assessment of E-journal impacts. Odlyzko (2002) argued that with the advent of new forms of web-based communication, the need for traditional peer review would decrease, and by the same token, novel forms of scrutinization and communication would emerge outside traditional journals (Odlyzko, 2002). Broadening this argument, Cronin (2001) held that despite the rich potential of these new forms of web-based assessment the need for conceptual scrutiny would prevail: „Undoubtedly, though, construct validity issues will continue to surface, as new forms of web-based invocation are factored into bibliometric evaluations and sociometric narratives of scientific communication.” (Cronin 2001).

Bar-Ilan (2001) introduced a first comprehensive review about the issue of data collection on the web, arguing that the web is by design a place of volatility and results may only be interpreted relative to the timeframe of conducting data collection. She also argued that search engines and tools available at that time would have to be assessed as inadequate to informetric purposes. Prime et al. (2002) analyzed differences between co-citations and co-stations and concluded that these should not be deemed as conceptual equivalents and analogies needed to be cautiously evaluated. Vaughan & Shaw (2003) made a similar point for bibliographic and web citation in general. User motivation and user behaviour studies (Ke, H. R. et al. 2002; Kim 2000; Wilkinson et al. 2003) and content-based analyses (Thelwall 2003) to understand hyperlinking behaviour emerged. In a different context, Lewison (2003) argued that citations to journal papers from clinical guidelines by the UK National Institute for Clinical Excellence (NICE) should be assessed as a complementary way of assessing broader research impact beyond the scientific domain.

Between 2003 and 2006 methodological scrutinizations reached a point that warranted extensive programmatic orientations through state-of-the-art reviews and framework concepts for webometrics/cybermetrics emerged (Thelwall et al. 2005). Conceptual reflection extended towards early webometric concepts such as the Web Impact Factor (Noruzi 2006), the need for understanding the use of new outlets of academic output such as online journals (McDonald 2007) or the relationship between self-promotion and visibility (Dietrich 2008) or underlying nature of web data in terms of its persistence over time (Bar-Ilan and Peritz 2004; Koehler 2004).

These first conceptualizations and reflections, we argue, structured the way new metrics of social media use in the scholarly landscape have been taken up. In the following (chapter 4), we hence want to shift the focus away from the general developments in cybermetrics and webometrics towards this new and specific form of web-based scholarly communication and evaluation that emerged during the years between 2009 and 2012. New platforms established that utilized data sources in a new way and opened new opportunities for analysis to the informetric and scientometric community. These years also

² As section 5 shows, this pattern has re-emerged with the scholarly establishment of scrutinization studies for Altmetrics.

witnessed the establishment and stabilization of new terminologies and concepts that influences scholarly discussion on the integration of web-based indicators to scientometrics. Through the use of social media and their influence on scholarly communities, it appears that broader issues come to the fore that the informetric and scientometric communities have not dealt with sufficiently (Marajo 2015; Bornmann 2016b). As we will see in the following sections (chapter 5 and 6), many arguments and conceptual differentiations in cybermetrics and webometrics re-emerged in debates about these new phenomena to be known by 'Altmetrics'.

4. The ‘Altmetrics’ landmark years 2009-2012

4.1. The establishment of the Altmetrics term

While there were many attempts to introduce new measures and motivations to utilize the web as a source for analysis and monitoring of scholarly activity (Almid and Ingwersen 1996; Almid and Ingwersen 1997; Bossy 1995), no dedicated terminology has been created for analysis of the social web between 2009 and 2012. It was in 2010, when the term ‘Altmetrics’ has been introduced by the information scientist Jason Priem in 2010, by claiming that he would prefer the term over other terms since it implies ‘a diversity of measures’.³ Shortly after, Priem together with his colleagues published a manifesto in which an understanding of Altmetrics has been coined that influenced the Altmetrics community sustainably: ‘That dog-eared (but uncited) article that used to live in a shelf now lives in Mendeley, CiteUlike, or Zotero – where we can see and count it. That hallway conversation about a recent finding has moved to blogs and social networks – now, we can listen in (...). This diverse group of activities forms a composite trace of impact far richer than any available before. We call the elements of this trace Altmetrics.’⁴

Up to now, its proponents regard Altmetrics as a powerful movement in science capable of revolutionizing the system of scientific performance measurement (Fenner 2014; Priem 2013). While other observers are more careful with triggering expectations (Gumpenberger et al. 2016; Haustein 2016a; Moore 2016), the diffusion of the topic amongst many different research communities cannot be denied (Gonzalez-Valiente et al. 2016). Since 2010, the literature on Altmetrics has grown enormously. Starting in open access journals such as PloS One and PloS Biology, the topic has soon been taken up by the informetric and scientometric community. Figure 1 provides an overview of the topics related to Altmetric, covering validation and scrutinization topics, but also scholarly social media use and its societal implications.

Despite its scholarly use there is, however, no common understanding, and hence no common definition of the term. According to the website of altmetric.com, an important provider of Altmetrics data, Altmetrics is defined as, ‘metrics and qualitative data that are complementary to traditional, citation-based metrics.’⁵ Another account at the same web site refers to Altmetrics as ‘the creation and study of new metrics based on the Social Web for analyzing, and informing scholarship’. According to Weller (2015), Altmetrics are primarily evaluation methods ‘that serve as alternatives to citation based metrics’, (Weller 2015). These examples for definitions demonstrate the unstable understanding of the term: While some of the definitions emphasize what alternative metrics measure, other metrics hint at what these measures aim at: they are set to change existing ways of assessing research and measuring scholarly impact.

According to Erdt et al (2016), most of the definitions differ regarding how Altmetrics can be traced, what is to be considered a relevant source, and how these sources can be handled. Haustein (2016) notes that part of the terminological confusion can be related to the notion of ‘alternative’ or more precisely, the ‘alt’ in Altmetrics (Haustein, Bowman, Costas 2016). Some scholars hence prefer to view Altmetrics as complementing existing scholarly metrics (Costas et al. 2014; Melero 2015) while others still propose that Altmetrics are part of an alternative research and publication system (Priem and Hemminger 2010; Priem and Hemminger 2012). Consequently, Altmetrics is not one, but many terms. Given its heterogeneity, the Altmetrics narrative has flourished among different policy and scientific communities, among which bibliometrics, information science, science communication, and library science are most important. This movement has been influenced by so called Altmetrics aggregators, that is, providers of Altmetrics information which are described in the following section.

³ I like the term [#articlelevelmetrics](#), but it fails to imply *diversity* of measures. Lately, I'm liking [#Altmetrics](#)”.³

⁴ <http://Altmetrics.org/manifesto/>

⁵ <https://www.altmetric.com/about-Altmetrics/what-are-Altmetrics/>

Figure 2: Publication sources in Altmetrics

Source: Erdt et al. 2016: 1133

4.2. Altmetric Providers

Altmetrics are provided by platforms, which collect data from different sources. These platforms offer services that go beyond optimization of individual scholarly visibility (Franzen 2015). Often they provide an application programmable interface (API) through which data collected by the platform can be publicly accessed. In informetric and scientometric studies on Altmetrics and Altmetrics aggregators (Costas et al. 2014), these are widely utilized though their data collection might be considered inconsistent in some cases (Zahedi et al. 2014). Furthermore, data collection strategies among the Altmetrics aggregators differ: While some of the Altmetrics aggregators collect their own data, others reuse previously collected data. Erdt et al. (2016) therefore distinguish between primary, secondary, and tertiary aggregators (see Figure 3). For individual and institutional users, widgets and bookmarks, visualization tools but increasingly also spam detection and gaming prevention are provided (Sangam 2015). Some of these providers (for instance, altmetric.com) particularly focus on quality assurance issues contributing to the emerging community standards debate in Altmetrics (Adie and Roe 2013). Furthermore, some of the Altmetrics aggregators monitor the development in the field by providing information about data sources and trends in blogs and feeds.

Figure 3: Altmetrics providers

Source: Erdt et al. 2016

Altmetrics aggregators are a recent but nevertheless dynamic phenomenon. The years between 2009 and 2012 can be seen as ‘landmark years’, in these years were launched that were capable of attracting millions of users and followers. Currently, there are mainly four providers which can be considered relevant:⁶ 1) Article Level Metrics (ALM) since 2009, 2) Impactstory 2011, Altmetric.com 2011, and Plum Analytics 2011.

Article Level Metrics (ALM) emerged from an initiative of the Public Library of Science (PLoS) to provide an alternative category for the classification of articles as citable or non-citable items (Das and Mishra 2014; Neylon and Wu 2009). This classification has been set up by Thomson Reuters to provide a basis for the calculation of the journal impact factor (Franzen 2015). The idea of ALM has been to find a different account of the value and quality of a single article (Lin and Fenner 2013). Launched in 2009, ALM now provides different impact and performance indicators, collecting data of different sources: Views, saves, discussions, recommendations, and citations, can be shown (Citrome 2015). Since PLoS ALM collects these data through on its own, Erdt et al. (2016) regard it as ‘primary aggregator. In addition, through the research tool Lagotto, PLoS provides further analytical features for its articles (Chamberlain 2013). Furthermore, PLoS collected data are accessible through application programming interfaces (APIs) and widgets for free download (Fenner 2013). However, these measures and data are restricted to those articles published in PLoS (Chamberlain 2013; Gordon et al. 2015).

Altmetric.com has been set up in 2011 as a commercial enterprise based in London to provide social media outreach for many different stakeholders such as groups, individual researchers, and publishers (Robinson-García et al. 2014). Its goal is to provide its customers information about which attention a single article receives (Franzen 2015). The measure is a composite indicator that combines different sources of data such as news, videos, policy documents, Facebook, twitter, LinkedIn, and Pinterest, resulting in a single indicator visualized by different colours which is often termed ‘altmetric donut’ (Gumpenberger et al. 2016). The measure is supposed to inform about both ‘the quantity (higher attention, higher score) and quality (weighting according to different sources) of attention received by each item, applying some kind of control for gaming’, (Costas et al. 2014). How the algorithm weighs the different sources is nevertheless hard to accomplish⁷ and has therefore been subject to criticism (Gumpenberger et al. 2016). According to Costas et al. (2014), altmetric.com covers data of more than

⁶ Erdt et al.(2016) list another four Altmetrics aggregators that are however too small to be considered relevant for this report.

⁷ <https://help.altmetric.com/support/solutions/articles/6000060969-how-is-the-altmetric-attention-score-calculated->

2.6 million papers since 2011. Furthermore, it provides social media scholars and the general public with access to its data through an intensely used API (Robinson-García et al. 2014). In the public debate of the Altmetrics movement, altmetric.com can maybe considered the most visible provider.

Impact story was launched in 2011 under the label ‘Total Impact’. It is a non-profit organization that emerged from a hackathon with the same name (total impact). Impact story now is an open source, person oriented, web based tool that aims at providing individual scientists with instruments to ‘sell their science’ (Araujo 2015), for instance by integrating outreach information into their CVs. It proposes to be ‘radically transparent’ and ‘open in communication’ (see impactstory.com). According to Erdt et al. (2016), some of the data Impactstory uses are reused from Altmetrics.com. Consequently, Impactstory is understood to be a ‘secondary aggregator’, (ibid.). The aim of its founding fathers Jason Priem and Heather Piwowar – who also revolutionized and irritated the community with their terminologies and concepts (Priem et al. 2012) - is to change the reputation structures of science by widening the scope of scientific products (Piwowar 2013). Impact story provides its users 5 categories for social outreach (cited, saved, discussed, viewed, and recommended). Since 2014, Impactstory charges its users a fee of 60 \$ per year (Franzen 2015).

PlumAnalytics was launched in the same year (2011) as a ‘for profit start up’ and has been set up to provide new scholarly measures. Data and measures are collected at the group level of organizations such as departments, museums, and labs. PlumAnalytics uses data of PloS ALM and is hence regarded to be a ‘secondary aggregator’ (Erdt et al. 2016). Since 2014, PlumAnalytics is part of EBSCO Information Services, a large provider of scientific information in the net. Similar to Impact Story and ALM, PlumAnalytics covers four categories of data: Usage, Captures, Mentions, Social Media, and Citations.

5. The current situation in Altmetrics

5.1. Commonly used data sources in Altmetrics

These providers of Altmetrics, which Erdt et al. (2016) have termed ‘aggregators’, measure different sources to provide social outreach information for scholars and institutional customers. They do not only provide Altmetrics data, by utilizing various social media platforms but also bibliometric information by sourcing large scientific databases such as WoS and Scopus. In the literature there is some confusion about how the activities and data collection practices can be interpreted and classified (Bornmann 2014a; Haustein 2016a). What does it mean, for instance, when downloads of an article are counted? To what scholarly activity does it refer? Priem and Henninger provided a first attempt of classifying and categorizing different data sources used by Altmetrics aggregators (Priem and Hemminger 2010). Since then, the Altmetrics landscape has been further developed and new data sources have been integrated. Most data sources, which are assigned to the categories provided in the following table, have millions of subscribers and users that allow for scientific information to travel beyond the typical audience of scholarly communication. According to Erdt et al. (2016), data sources used in Altmetrics can be assigned to the following categories: Social bookmarking; video, photo and slide sharing; Social networks; blogging; microblogging; recommendation and review systems; Q & A; Online Encyclopedias; Online digital libraries; Dataset repositories; Online publishers; Search engines and blog aggregators; others. The following table provides an overview of data sources and categories.

Table 1: sources used by altmetric providers

Categories	Data sources
Social bookmarking	CiteULike, Mendeley, Delicious
Video, photo and slide sharing	Youtube, Vimeo, Slideshare, Flickr, Daily Motion
Social networks	Facebook, Google+, LinkedIn, Academia, ResearchGate
Blogging	Nature blogs, PloS blogs, Scientific American blogs, Research Blogging, Nature
Microblogging	Twitter, Sina Weibo, Tumblr
Recommendation and review systems	F1000, F1000Prime, Reddit, Publons, Amazon reviews, Goodreads,
Q & A	Stack exchange, other
Online digital libraries and repositories	PMC, Europe PMC, BioMed Central, PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science, CrossRef, Fighshare, arXiv, WorldCat, institutional repositories, RePec, EBSCO, SSRN, EPrints, dSpace, USPTO Patents, Lexis, CRIS
Dataset repositories	Dryad, Datacite, ADS
Source code repositories	Github, Sourceforge, Bitbucket
Online publishers	PLoS, Open Edition, Copernicus
Search engines, blog aggregators	Science seeker
Other	ORCID, Google code, Google patents, WIPO, bit.ly, COUNTER

Source: adopted by Priem and Henninger (2010), Erdt et.al.(2016), Haustein et al.(2016)

As the following table indicates, Erdt et al. (2016) have (based on Priem and Henninger 2010) provided a first overview that covers most of the data sources used in Altmetrics. Notwithstanding, this overview provides little understanding of what these categories actually show, and consequently how they are to be understood. A deeper understanding of these sources is needed in order to harvest their use for opening up the research to broader societal audiences. A more systematic account of how to understand data sources in Altmetrics has been provided by Haustein et al. (Haustein, Bowman, Costas 2016) who frame the different function that can be attributed to research objects in data sources as ‘access, appraise, and apply (ibid.:5). By using such concepts, informetric and scientometric scholars acknowledge that the data collected by Altmetrics provided express different social and behavioural repertoires and relate to different forms of order. Erdt et al. term these sorts of behaviour collected by aggregators APIs ‘events tracked’ (Erdt et al. 2016). Relating to Haustein et al. (2016), access events are understood as events ‘showing interest in a research object’ such as reading something in Mendeley or downloading information on CiteUlike. By appraisal events, Haustein et al. (2016) understand comments, reviews or debates in which a research object is put in relation to other objects, which can be done both quantitatively (reddit) or qualitatively (F1000Prime). Apply events use these events to start something different such as a new community or a new network (ibid.). However, this account does also not appear to be sufficient since the differentiation of events in social media use does not explain why some data sources are chosen by its users, collected by Altmetrics aggregators, and utilized by informetricians while others are not and what that means for the evolving landscape of Altmetrics landscape. To provide a first systematic account of these dependencies, we suggest referring to the framework of the sociology of valuation.

The sociology of (e-) valuation is concerned with how people ascribe worth to objects and on what basis such valuation is done. The basis for such theory making is the observation of the importance of evaluation in different fields of society (Power 1997) where the need for reducing uncertainty and complexity leads to increasing practices of assessing performance. In this respect, heterogeneous phenomena of attributing value to objects, practices, and people, and of assessing their value (Kjellberg and Mallard 2013; Lamont 2012), have become a popular subject in this stream of research (Beckert and Aspers 2011; Bowker and Star 1999; Espeland and Stevens 2008; Heintz 2016; Lamont 2009; Zelizer 2011). According to this scholarship, categorization and classification becomes most important: As a valuation practice, classification facilitates the construction of categories that make different empirical phenomena commensurable and/or allow for arranging objects, practices, and people into a hierarchical order. Categorization and classification are thus crucial ingredients for evaluations.

Such reflections are most important for the landscape that arises with the establishment of Altmetrics and its contribution to existing measures in scientometrics and bibliometrics. In bibliometrics, data sources such as publications or citations are ascribed value since, as indicators of scientific performance, they serve to refer to categories of evaluation. Now, with the rise of Altmetrics, new data sources are added to these indicators and relating to Lamont (2012), the questions arises how they are categorized and to what value they refer.⁸ At the same time, the establishment of these categories are themselves based on acts of valuation. The construction of categories and their arrangement into a particular order highlight specific qualities that become infused with value and thus become regarded as relevant for measuring empirical phenomena. In other words, value attributions in classifications and categorizations even in its simplest forms cannot be separated from practices of producing and collecting data; data practices go with acts of valuation. Such a view towards categorization and valuation needs to reflect both the production and the consumption side of scientific information. Each of the choices for a dissemination channel (such as publications, blogs, or videos) and its reception can be regarded as ‘act of valuation’ of an issue in science and scholarly communication.

Scientists attribute value by transforming their findings into specific audience specific formats. There are, we propose, specific media immanent value-attributions that are enacted with every such transformation. Some media formats are attributed to produce publics while others are referred as the formats for entertainment. These acts of valuation are two-sided. They have an effect for those who

⁸ Recently, in this respect, it has been argued that Altmetrics point to ‘broader societal impact’ instead of scientific performance, Bornmann (2014a, 2016a)

produce such transformations, that is, for the scholars that place their accounts in twitter or YouTube. At the same time, they also affect the reception of scientific information for those who refer to knowledge items or research objects that are communicated through these channels. The combination between the reciprocal effects of production and consumption makes these channels relevant for Altmetrics providers. In reverse, the choice of data sources by the different Altmetrics provider further increases value of these sources for scholars using social media since their outreach can now be calculated and contribute positively to their standing. Without considering the value attributed to channels of dissemination both by producers and by recipients, the worth of Altmetrics, and hence their categorization cannot sufficiently be grasped. Transforming Marshall McLuhan famous dictum to the study of valuation, these attribution logic can be termed as: “the medium is the worth” (of the channel). To reflect about these functions, utilizations and value attributions can be perceived as one of the key assets of this report for librarians and librarian scientists.

Some of the most recent reviews about the landscape of Altmetrics and social media use in science have reported about the function of some data sources (Sugimoto et al. forthcoming). However, the analyses of data sources such as YouTube or twitter are not always related to its utilization in Altmetrics and Altmetrics providers. Notwithstanding, they are rapidly taken up by scholars- though in different intensity – and questions arise, whether these sources which are themselves platforms might shape or even change scholarly behaviour.

The first data source for Altmetrics providers that emerged in the social media landscape are online repositories and pre-publication services. For example, Arxiv.org (launched in 1991) has been set up strategically to provide an alternative to the established journal publication system. Started with archiving articles from physics, Arxiv.org soon broadened its disciplinary spectrum by including computer science and biology. Articles can be submitted via the system and do not pass a peer review procedure. The process provided by arxiv.org is supposed to be faster than the submission and publication system. Furthermore, articles are easily accessible and free of charge. Recent studies have explored the increasing relationship between arXiv and the wider scholarly social media landscape (Bar-Ilan 2014; Cassidy R. Sugimoto et al. 2014; Priem et al. 2012).

A second provider of scientific information that is utilized by Altmetrics providers is Biomedcentral. BMC emerged as an open access publishing house that covers disciplines in the biomedical field with journals such as BMC Medicine or BMC biology.⁹ In the years following, the publishing houses and professional associations joined in and further broadened the landscape: In 2000, Pubmed Central was launched by the National Institutes of Health as a free of charge full text archive.¹⁰ Through its user interface, articles from participating publishers and journals can be accessed through its user interface. Financed by the reputed NIH, PMC grants credibility to those journals who decide to store content at PMC. In addition, PMC provides further services with cross reference software. The impact of these new publishing houses and online repositories on scholarly social media landscape appears to be undeniable; however, its relationship has only rarely be explored. (Stewart et al. 2013)

Today, these data sources are widely covered by Altmetrics aggregators. PubmedCentral, for instance, is covered by all four dominant Altmetrics players. Altmetrics providers and online repositories share the goal of contributing to an alternative system of scholarly communication. The landscape of additional data sources utilized by the Altmetrics aggregators is, however, much more diverse. The following compilation informed by recent reviews (Erdt et al. 2016; Haustein, Bowman, Costas 2016; Sugimoto et al. forthcoming) provides an overview of these different sources and attempts to interpret how these different channels and their value for scholarly communication can be understood.

⁹ www.biomedcentral.com/about (last accessed Nov.21st 2016)

¹⁰ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/>

5.2. The use of data sources as acts of valuation

5.2.1. “Doing Science” and “Science made Public”: Social Media, blogging and microblogging

The most debated acts of valuation in the choice of dissemination channels for scholarly social media communication are those processes aiming at what is commonly referred as popularization (Kidd 1988), and sometimes even marketing work (Mahrt and Puschmann 2014). The increasing visibility and diffusion of social media channels of blogging and microblogging sites accessible to the public both by form and content (Bonetta 2007) has been understood by some scholars to be an expression of ‘broader societal impact’ of social media (Bornmann 2014a). Such claims have been made since traditionally popularization work is considered not to be done by scientists themselves, but by journalists and media specialists who transfer knowledge from academia to the public (Dubois 1986; Kidd 1988). Currently, however, scientists themselves increasingly utilize different genres and formats to gain public legitimacy and understanding for their work (Myers 2003). These activities are more reflected with the rise of dedicated formats and channels of dissemination for science communication to the public (Haustein, Bowman, Costas 2016). Consequently, Social Media, blogging, and microblogging sites have been explored by a bulk of studies: Science blogs and its audience reactions have been widely explored (Kouper 2010; Mahrt and Puschmann 2014; Riesch and Mendel 2013)

Altmetrics providers have observed this development and built upon the fact that social media, blogging and microblogging activities are utilized in science communication, and what is more, have become increasingly visible among the public (Franzen 2015). In turn, it appears, Altmetrics instruments have further accelerated this use of social media and they have made the valuation act of ‘making things public’ more reflexive (Haustein 2016a). Blogging sites are widely used by academics (Puschmann and Mahrt 2012). Interview data suggest that these formats are strategically chosen by scientists as a means of popularization (Mahrt and Puschmann 2014). Not surprisingly, science blogs often discuss scientific problems taking more general stances such as criticizing academic culture (Mewburn and Thomson 2013) or relating to grand narratives such as the ‘grand challenges’ rhetoric (Kaldewey 2013). These genre specific uses of narratives could, as some observers suggest, contribute to shaping new scholarly identities (EWINS 2005) even in traditional fields such as the humanities (Potter 2012; Puschmann and Bastos 2015) or behaviour that does not relate to established forms academic politeness (Luzon 2011). Blogging sites therefore also have functions for the scholarly community (Puschmann and Mahrt 2012): Kjellberg, for instance, particularly insists on the reviewing and informing function of the blogging format (Kjellberg 2010). These examples demonstrate that blogging activities seems to blur existing boundaries between popularization and professional scholarly communication, or even as Sugimoto et al.(forthcoming) put it produce a ‘tension between traditional and alternative (democratic) means of research dissemination (Bowman 2015a).

For Altmetrics scholars, blogs, science blogs, and micro blogging sites are important since they are highly utilized in aggregator platforms (Hank et al. 2014; Kabilan et al. 2010; Nentwich and König 2014; Ringelhan et al. 2015). What is more, they are also considered as particularly valuable for scholars (Boyd and Ellison 2007). This becomes particularly apparent in the calculating practices of the composite indicator of altmetric.com where blogs and aggregator platforms are integrated. But among the textual forms of disseminating research, particularly microblogging and social network activities of researchers are covered by the Altmetrics aggregators, sourced by utilizing large providers (Haustein, Larivière et al. 2014).

Social networking sites are specific in that they allow users to construct as presentation of their self which can be shared among others, and that allows for analyzing views and connection (Boyd and Ellison 2007). Among the network sites, Facebook (2004) is the most important (Bar-Ilan et al. 2012; Nentwich and König 2014; Thelwall and Kousha 2015c). Particularly for professional use, Facebook becomes a relevant scholarly dissemination channel that is far more important than for instance LinkedIn because LinkedIn is mostly used for professional purposes only, while in Facebook the boundaries between personal and professional use are blurred (Procter et al. 2010). This is relevant since the percentage of researchers who use social network sites for professional use is lower than for

personal reasons (Loeb et al. 2014). Data from Facebook are collected by all four big Altmetrics providers while data from Google+ data are harvested only by Altmetric.com and PlumAnalytics¹¹ (Erdt et al. 2016). In the meantime, special scholarly social network sites have emerged that provide special services for researchers such as ResearchGate which is also increasingly used by the scientometric and informetric community (Hoffmann et al. 2016a; Hoffmann et al. 2016b; Kraker and Lex 2015; Onyanha 2015; Orduna-Malea et al. 2016b; Thelwall and Kousha 2015a). Such scholarly social network sites become increasingly relevant for digital self-marketing in the web (van Noorden 2014; Veletsianos 2012).

A second relevant social media activity that is increasingly popular among academics is microblogging. Microblogging practices have emerged from the need to shorten online messages and soon became popular also in the academic sphere. Posts from these are termed ‘microblogs’ because the amount of characters in a post is restricted (for instance twitter restricts a post to 140 characters). Most important platforms for microblogging in science are Twitter (launched in 2006), and Sina Weibo (a Chinese platform). Microblogging posts from Sina Weibo, however, are only rarely used for scholarly purposes (Gonzalez-Valiente et al. 2016). Among these Twitter is the most important (Micieli and Micieli 2012; Thelwall et al. 2013). Scholars use these platforms mainly to announce new articles or books. Although most of the uses for microblogs are passive (Carpenter et al. 2012), and overrated in scholarly influence, sources such as Twitter tend to provide full names of their users (Bowman 2015b; Chretien et al. 2011) which in turn makes them interesting for Altmetrics aggregators. Increasingly, such developments are observed by scholarly communities who provide their members with tools how to use these platforms for presenting their research (Micieli and Micieli 2012). Given the often informal character of the posts, however, scholarly microblogging activities are perceived to blur the boundaries between professional and personal (Bowman 2015a).

There are, however, more specific blogs that emerged as data sources since 2006: the non-profit source ‘Science Blogs’ emerged in early 2006. In 2011, the ‘Scientific American Blogs’ has been set up to widen the scope of the popular journal’s audience. The biggest player in the dedicated science blog community is “Research Blogger” (Shema et al. 2012, 2015). Research Blogger can be itself perceived as an aggregator in the science blogosphere. All of the blogs collected at Research Blogger post content that references peer reviewed research. Consequently, scientific blogs that are aggregated in Research Blogger are increasingly considered a relevant scientific source. Being cited in a blog is hence also regarded as being similar to citations. (Haustein, Bowman, Costas 2016)

By collecting and listing these blogs, first studies indicate (Harley et al. 2010; Shema et al. 2015), Research Blogger fulfils a legitimating function since it grants credibility to other blogs through the use of the RB icon. At the same this legitimating function feeds back to the Altmetrics aggregators using RB to whom such legitimacy is transferred. This finding further indicates that the use of specific platforms affect the reception of scientific content since they are attributed value: According to recent studies, one third of the German research staff at universities (Puschmann and Mahrt 2012), and more than one fifth of British doctoral students (Carpenter et al. 2012) are paying attention to these science blogs.

5.2.2. Explaining and Entertaining: Multimedia Content & Slides

A second act of valuation that data sources from altmetric aggregators provide can be termed ‘explaining and entertaining’. There is increasing use of audiovisual material as dissemination channels for science communication (Kousha et al. 2012; Welbourne and Grant 2016). Erdt et al. (2016) have termed data sources that can be assigned to this value attribution to the category ‘video, photo, and slide sharing’ (see table 1). In the past ten years, specific platforms have emerged for the sharing of pictures, such as slides (Slideshare, launched in 2006), photos, and pictures (Pinterest and Figshare, launched in 2010 and 2011, respectively). Other picture data bases such as Flickr are only seldom used by aggregators (Erdt et al. 2016). Furthermore, there are platforms that make audio-visual material available. Vimeo, established in 2004 and YouTube 2005 are for instance sources that are referred in this category.

¹¹ In order to compete with Facebook, Google launched Google+ in 2011, but its diffusion is far less pervasive than initially expected.

Studies on picture only platforms in scholarly communication are rare: Empirical examinations exist for slideshare (Mas-Bleda et al. 2014). Instead, most interest goes to Youtube (Kousha et al. 2012; Sugimoto et al. 2013; Sugimoto et al. forthcoming; Tsou et al. 2014). This could be an expression of youtube dominance in the data collection services of Altmetrics providers: With the exception of PloS ALM, all aggregators make use of YouTube as a data source. At the same, this reflects its increasing role as medium of dissemination.

However, the value of these platforms and channels for their audiences is far more than simply the provision of additional sources in slides and pictures as the categorization of Erdt et al. (2016) suggests (see table 2). Rather, these formats are becoming influential because they are attributed valuable for what is called infotainment. There are, for instance, specific channels that have emerged in YouTube (Welbourne and Grant 2016). According to Sugimoto et al., for instance, one of the most famous products in this respect are TED talks and TED conferences (Sugimoto et al. 2013). The diffusion and success of TED cannot be explained without taking the success of its channel into account: According to Sugimoto et al, by utilizing YouTube channels for their purposes, TED is able to strategically analyze its audience (Tsou et al. 2014). The availability of user comments in these channels (Thelwall, Sud et al. 2012) allows them to strategically adapt to their needs. Again, the value of such sources emerges from both sides of the supply and demand side for their attribution. From the supply side, it can be argued scholars use these channels strategically to label their products as entertaining or explanatory. At the contrary, from the demand side, the entertaining value further increases the motivation of users to select these sources (Kousha et al. 2012): They are not only informative but also entertaining.

5.2.3. Organizing Attribution: Reference Management and Recommending

Some proponents in the Altmetrics literature have pointed out, that Altmetrics have claimed to better fulfil the task of focusing attention to specific research products not communicable in existing scholarly communication formats (Franzen 2015; Priem 2013, 2014; Priem et al. 2012). In the bibliometric literature, the attribution of this task of attention and influence has been traditionally assigned to citations (Moed 2005) which contributed to the selection of literature (Hornbostel 1997). However, with the flourishing of social media use, platforms have emerged that provide an alternative route to article selection (Priem and Hemminger 2010). In the social media landscape that is utilized by Altmetrics aggregators, research is increasingly recommended through channels of cognitive homophily, that is, platforms of scholars with of similar backgrounds, similar disciplines, similar taste regarding the presentation of arguments (Kurtz and Henneken 2012). One of the first platforms that came up in 2004 was CiteUlike with the slogan 'Read what your peers read'. In a similar vein, Mendeley was launched to provide online resources for bibliographic information which is at the same time visible to other users (Gunn 2013). According to Erdt et al.(2016) and Sugimoto et al. (Sugimoto et al. forthcoming), Mendeley is the most popular source which is covered by Altmetrics aggregators directly (Mohammadi et al. 2015). Mendeley is also the data source which is covered most in the Altmetrics literature (Bar-Ilan 2014; Gunn 2013; Haustein, Larivière et al. 2014; Jeng et al. 2015; Judit Bar-ilan 2014; Maflahi and Thelwall 2016a) while CiteUlike has been only rarely covered (Haustein, Peters, Bar-Ilan et al. 2014). All these sources data sources for reference management provide access; by providing information on scholarly usage, such platforms may influence selection decisions of scientists.

The selection process becomes more rigorous when scientific is attributed intellectual influence or intellectual relevance. According to Sugimoto et al. (forthcoming), for instance, F1000Prime can be regarded as a resource for selection of 'important' articles in the biomedical realm. In this regard, it has been explored by various Altmetrics studies (Bornmann 2014b; Bornmann and Leydesdorff 2013; Desai et al. 2014). The credibility of the source is achieved by nominating more than 5000 scholars who evaluate this research. Based upon these reviews, research is rated as 'good', 'very good', and 'exceptional'. Given that there is no negative rate such as bad or worst, Haustein et al. (2016) understand the act of 'reviewed on F1000' as 'appraisal,' (ibid:5). New practices of peer review emerge in post publication approaches and in platforms such as Publons¹² that are attributed to be 'open' and more 'transparent. However, their acceptance in the scientific community appears to be limited (Adie 2009).

¹² <http://home.publons.com/>

A second online data source that becomes important in recommending scholarly literature and data is reddit.com.¹³ Reddit was founded in 2005 by Huffman, Ohanian, and Swartz. Reddit can be considered as an aggregator for social news, musings and discussion that yet does not focus exclusively on scholarly communication. Reddit allows registered users to upload content either provided in textual format or as a weblink. In both cases, users can evaluate these posts positively or negatively which subsequently influences its position, that is, its visibility on the reddit homepage. Reddit has been only rarely covered in the literature; according to Thelwall et al. (Thelwall et al. 2013) it can be considered as an influential social media platform.

5.2.4. Empowering Reproducibility: Sharing Data and Code

Sharing data appears to refer to the normative frame of organized scepticism since according to Merton (Merton 1972), the ethos of science expects scholars to be sceptical of each others works. The first online sharing data platforms have been introduced in the late 1990s (Sourceforge: 1999¹⁴). More recently, the sharing of data has been acknowledged by journals and funding agencies. Through sharing platforms, various sorts of data can be transferred and exchanged. Moreover, they encourage the engage in improving the data quality and data analysis quality. Github (launched in 2008) can be considered as the most advanced provider for data sharing (Dabbish et al. 2012). Other data repositories allow for citing data that also strengthens reproducibility. At the same time, such utilizations can be read from a normative framework as presenting oneself as ideal ‘scepticism’, (Haustein, Bowman, Costas 2016).

According to Sugimoto, however, the use of these sharing platforms is still low and so is their diffusion amongst the altmetric aggregators. Figshare, for instance is only visited regularly by 0.5%. Consequently, the use of such platforms for data and code sharing are quite different among the Altmetrics aggregators: While Altmetric.com does not use any of these sources, Impact Story, and PlumAnalytics both use Dryad and Github. Most intensely, sharing platforms are acknowledged by PloS ALM who do not only collect data from Dryad (launched in 2008) and Github, but also DataCite (launched in 2009), ADS, and Bitbucket.

5.2.5. Empowering Others and Signifying Expertise: Q&A Forums

From a normative perspective, empowering others by providing expertise can be regarded to refer to the mertonian norms of communalism and disinterestedness. According to these, since scientists are interested only in the progress of knowledge, helping others to strengthen their scientific capacities would contribute to the social power of science. Moreover, such acts of service can be reciprocal since scientists with expertise may encounter problems when they want to dig into new terrains of knowledge where they have less experience.

Social media have been particularly appraised for their focus on such participatory activities and their contribution the reciprocity of knowledge exchange (Taylor 2013). Many Q & A Forums have been established through which scholars that post questions are provided with sufficient answers. The quality of these answers, however, is difficult to measure since those users seldom provide their names and users also do not report whether they are satisfied. Yet, as most platforms provide an up- and downvote mechanism, we it can be assessed which solution or comment seems to be most plausible or fit for the purpose. This in transparency is easily understood since posing –mostly technical– questions does not provide immediate reputation. At the same time, answering questions cannot be regarded as an efficient channel of dissemination since most of the questions are very specific and addressed to the needs of a particular user although they are visible for other users. This might correspond to low interest in the scholarly analysis of this type of dissemination channels. In their recent review, Sugimoto et al. do not report relevant research that dealt with Q & A Forums.

Consequently, Altmetrics aggregators make considerably rarely use of Q & A providers: Impact story, PloS ALM, and the smaller aggregators such as Kudos, and Snowball metrics make no use of Q & A forums. The only notable exception is the research platform ‘stack exchange’ which was launched in 2008. Stack exchange characterizes itself as a ‘network of Q & A communities’ that is bound together by

¹³ <https://www.reddit.com/>

¹⁴ <https://sourceforge.net/>

its interest in strengthening collaborative software development and analytics. Its most reputed community is stack overflow specifically designed to developer's needs. Stack Exchange now can be perceived to be a reputed data source which has attracted manifold scholarly attention, particularly those from mathematics, statistics, physics and computer science. However, studies on user interface, audience, coverage or validation of stack overflow and stack exchange are limited (Begel et al. 2013).

5.2.6. Stabilizing Knowledge: Online Encyclopedias & Guidelines

Similarly to Q & A forums, working in collaborative knowledge production systems is appreciated by the social media community. Wikipedia has emerged as the biggest online encyclopaedia system that provides content for almost any field of knowledge. Established in 2001, Wikipedia crowdsources content from users all over the world. According to Sugimoto et al., Wikipedia has gained credibility also among the field of scholarly experts and professionals (Chesney 2006). Hence, it is increasingly used by scholars as a relevant source especially at the beginning of a research project. Notwithstanding, Wikipedia is the only source for Online Encyclopaedias that is used among the main Altmetrics aggregators (Zahedi et al. 2014). Studies of online repositories hence mainly focused on Wikipedia (Black 2008; Bould et al. 2014; Butler 2008; Chesney 2006; Nielsen 2007b; PLOS ALM et al. 2014)

There are however, limitations for contributions to this source since Wikipedia does not provide reward for authorship in the way the traditional scientific publishing system does with citations (Black 2008). Consequently, the choice of Wikipedia can be regarded as a dissemination channel stabilizing the communalism dimension of knowledge. At the same time, given the limited set of academic contributors, Wikipedia is still perceived to be a rather “nerdy” dissemination channel from the side of scholarly producers.

5.2.7. Supporting Policy: Policy Documents

Informing policy and influencing decisions can be regarded as one of the most notable effects of scientific research. In the Altmetrics literature, we concurrently find the notion of societal influence that is attributed to Altmetrics, particularly when low correlation with citation is put in front (Bornmann 2014b, 2016a). Thus, the influence on policy is an important asset associated to the notion of broader societal influence. Policy document literature, however, is not sufficiently covered by the main scientific databases and increasingly scholars have begun how to deal with this (Simons 2016), given the policy relevance of many emerging subjects such as higher education policy (Nokkala 2015) or climate policy (Pregernig 2014).

Policy documents are hence considered highly relevant by the Altmetrics aggregators. Altmetric.com, for instance rates policy documents higher than most of the social media platforms. A mention in a policy document increases the score of the altmetric.com composite indicator by three points.¹⁵ There is, however, no indication of how policy documents are found. In the description of the calculation, Altmetrics.com gives the example of a US and a UK governmental document. Does that mean that only policy documents in English language are sourced while documents in French, Chinese, or German are ignored? Which governmental agencies are covered?

According to Erdt et al. (2016), no other aggregator mentions policy documents directly, although websites and news articles used by Plum analytics indicate that policy relevance might in principle be appreciated. That indicates that although policy relevance can be regarded a specific value of scientific information and research objects, there are no dedicated channels of dissemination that are linked to the Altmetrics landscape.

5.3. Summary Acts of Value – What is counted and why?

Summarizing, different channels of dissemination, platforms, forums, repositories, and blogs have been established which make up an emerging digital scholarly literature apart or complementary to the established publishing system. Altmetrics aggregators are but some of the notable players which shape these activities, in which often scholarly and non-scholarly, professional and personal boundaries

¹⁵ <https://help.altmetric.com/support/solutions/articles/6000060969-how-is-the-altmetric-attention-score-calculated->

become blurred. Interestingly, not all of these sources are utilized and harvested in a similar way even if in public debate they are highly visible. In the existing scholarly literature that discusses this development (Erdt et al. 2016; Franzen 2015; Haustein, Bowman, Costas 2016; Sugimoto et al. forthcoming), we can find no accounts as to how these choices and selections by aggregators can be understood.

While blogging and microblogging activities are considered relevant by Altmetrics providers as the table of Erdt et al., suggests, other forms of content such as wikis are considered less relevant. Facebook and Twitter are covered in all Altmetrics platforms. At the contrary, online repositories and digital libraries are used in different types of data sources by all Altmetrics aggregators such as PMC, Pubmed and BiomMedCentral, this does not apply in the same way for data sharing platforms and sites for code sharing such as DataCite, Sourceforge or Github. The same goes for Q & A forums which are not considered as relevant data sources for altmetric aggregators such as Impact story, PloS ALM, and the smaller aggregators such as Kudos, and Snowball metrics. It appears that particularly those channels are highlighted that relate to the existing academic reward system that is being shaped by a ubiquitous citation culture.

In this report, however, we have argued that the choice for these channels of dissemination both for production and consumption of scientific information can be regarded as acts of valuation that attribute additional or more specific value to the research object. In the case of scientific blogs it appears, that value is not only attributed from the academic realm since mostly peer reviewed literature is reported and authors are usually identified with their full names; it also the representation in the public media where scientific blogs are referred as legitimate and credible sources of science communication and popularization. These processes may have led to the emergence of further aggregating platforms such as Research Blogger that may have not taken place, for instance, in the realm of Q & A forums.

The acts of valuation argument becomes even more convincing in what Erdt et al. (2016) have termed the category of sharing of pictures, photo and slide sharing (ibid: 125). While providing picture, photo and slides are more attached to the academic culture, it appears that these resources are not used by the users of the platforms. Altmetric aggregators hence make limited use of slide, picture and photo sharing platforms: Slideshare is not considered a data source for altmetric.com and PloS ALM. Pinterest is only used by altmetric.com while PlumAnalytics, Impactstory, and PloS do not make use of this source.

Instead, youtube is – with the exception of PloS ALM- provided by all altmetric aggregators (see also Erdt et al. 2016). We have argued that this selection can be understood by relating to the entertaining and explaining value that is attributed to this audio-visual channel. Users expect videos in Youtube science channels to be more explanatory and entertaining than other channels. At the same time, the feedback of the audience can easily be harvested by the Altmetric aggregators. Thus, it appears that these channels of dissemination provide additional value for both recipients and producers apart of their closeness to the academic reward system.

6. Altmetrics under review – validation and scrutinization

The biggest share in literature and research on Altmetrics make up studies on scrutinizing and validating Altmetrics. As Figure 2 suggests, these topics have even increased in the more recent years (see Figure 4). One of the reasons why scrutinization is such a dominant theme in studying Altmetrics,

is the frequently repeated claim of its proponents to provide alternatives to scholarly impact measures (Priem and Hemminger 2012). Although the claim was also made to broaden the study of scholarly impact 'beyond the paper' (Priem 2013) to other types and objects of scientific activity such as scholarly talks, data, and blogs, the comparison to existing measures appeared to be most fascinating among scholars in informetrics and bibliometrics. The increasing use of social media has further contributed to this question.

Figure 4: Overview of topics in Altmetrics

Source: Erdt et al.2016:1133

Consequently, many studies of validation for Altmetrics concentrate on the following topics (Erdt et al. 2016: 1133): 1st) the coverage of articles with mentions in social media platforms, 2nd) their intensity, 3rd) scrutinization studies that compare Altmetrics with traditional measures of scholarly performance and influence (citations). As Costas, Zahedi and Wouters point out, these studies have at least found some correlations 'suggesting that these two approaches are somehow related but not the same' (Costas et al. 2014: 2004). The studies differ, however, in the way comparisons are accomplished. Some studies focus on a specific Altmetrics aggregator such as altmetric.com in order to compare different social media data with other bibliometric information consistently (Costas et al. 2014). In this group, particularly, we mainly find coverage and correlation studies where social media data are analyzed according to what extent they cover scientific articles and how they relate to citations among these articles.

Other studies concentrate on a single social media data source such as Mendeley (Gunn 2013; Thelwall and Sud 2016), Facebook (Nentwich and König 2014; Ringelhan et al. 2015) or Academia.edu (Thelwall and Kousha 2014) in order to explore significant characteristics and structures of that media use and its (scholarly) audience, and a third group of studies compares the relationships and or correlation between different social media or Altmetrics data sources (Gunn 2013; Li et al. 2012).

Based upon their designs and research goals, they draw different conclusions and interpretations from their results. Particularly in the group of correlation studies with existing bibliometric and scientometric indicators, we find a pattern of argumentation that assigns social media use scholarly impact when high correlation can be approved, and the attribution of broader societal impact in cases where such

correlation is low (Haustein, Sugimoto et al. 2015), which is the case for most of the scholarly used social media.

6.1. Social Media, blogging and microblogging

Overall, scholarly documents are only rarely mentioned on Facebook and other social media platforms (Costas et al. 2014; Priem et al. 2012). In some fields, however, such as the social sciences and the biomedical community, scholarly papers are more frequently highlighted (Costas et al. 2014). The correlations with citations are, however, weak among all fields of study whereas correlation with other Altmetrics counts are higher (Costas et al. 2014). According to Sugimoto et al. (forthcoming), one exception is the academic social network ResearchGate which correlates higher with citations. Up to now, there are few studies reporting about ResearchGate (Hoffmann et al. 2016b; Jordan 2015, Orduna-Malea et al. 2016a, 2016b).

Low coverage and low correlation with citations can also be observed in scientific blogs. Different to other types of social media, blogs frequently cite scholarly peer reviewed literature (Shema and Bar-Ilan 2014). Therefore, blog citations are also investigated in scrutinization studies (Shema and Bar-Ilan 2014; Shema et al. 2014). According to (Priem et al. 2012), PloS articles show the highest coverage while WoS articles are much less covered (less than 2%). Citations in blogs are, however, a good proxy for identifying highly cited journal publications (Shema et al. 2014). There are some indications that blogging cites are more correlated to other types of impact such as mentions in the press (Shema and Bar-Ilan 2014). According to Sugimoto et al. (forthcoming), these studies suffer from overrepresentation of highly cited literature.

Microblogging coverage in Twitter related to scholarly papers appears to be low, but higher than in other types of social media platforms (Alhoori et al. 2014; Costas et al. 2014; Hammarfelt 2014; Haustein, Costas et al. 2015; Haustein, Peters, Sugimoto et al. 2014). Coverage varies depending on the type of source and discipline (Costas et al. 2014; Holmberg and Thelwall 2014), but tends to be generally higher for PloS articles (Barthel et al. 2015). Studies that focus on correlations between twitter and citations counts provide a heterogeneous picture, depending whether specific disciplines or large-scale corpora have been studied. Priem and Piwowar et al., for instance, report low correlations between 0.1 and 0.2 (Priem et al. 2012). A specificity of twitter is the short time window of coverage or chance of coverage (Eysenbach 2011; Shuai et al. 2012). Scholarly documents are mentioned on Twitter usually only short after their publication (Eysenbach 2011; Shuai et al. 2012). A study by Haustein and Costas et al. though revealed that more of the papers published in 2012 had been cited than tweeted by the end of 2013 (Haustein, Costas et al. 2015). Productivity studies have compared twitter output with other types of more traditional scholarly output (Haustein, Bowman, Holmberg et al. 2016). Yet, the initial assumption that those scholars tweeting much publish less could however not be validated.

6.2. Multimedia Content & Slides

Multimedia content, videos, and picture sharing sites are only covered by a few scrutinization studies due to methodological problems. Thelwall and Kousha, for instance argue that it is more appropriate to count views as a proxy to impact rather than citations (Thelwall, Kousha et al. 2012). Accordingly, Sugimoto et al. (2016) have studied YouTube channels of TEDtalks and revealed that they are highly viewed but only rarely cited. In addition, commenting on TEDtalk channels was high, with academics receiving more comments than non-academics (Sugimoto et al. 2013). A more recent study of science communication on YouTube revealed that user generated and consistent science communicators received more attention than professionally produced content without a regular communicator (Welbourne and Grant 2016).

6.3. Organizing Attribution: Reference Management and Recommending

Mendeley has received the most attention in terms of studies dealing with this data source for scrutinization and cross-validation purposes (Bornmann and Haunschild 2016b; Haunschild and Bornmann 2016; Maflahi and Thelwall 2016b; Maleki 2015b; Mohammadi et al. 2016b; Thelwall and

Sud 2016; Thelwall and Wilson 2016). These data suggest highest rate for document coverage among the social media platforms for reference management. Notwithstanding, other reference manager and bookmarking perform worse than Mendeley (Bar-Ilan et al. 2012; Priem et al. 2012). The coverage is yet dependent on the Altmetrics aggregator (Knight 2014; Robinson-García et al. 2014), journal (Li et al. 2012), and field (Mohammadi and Thelwall 2014; Mohammadi et al. 2016b).

Readings in Mendeley and citations are higher correlated than other types of data sources utilized for Altmetrics. For instance, correlations between the Reference Management CiteULike and citations are lower than for Mendeley (Bar-Ilan et al. 2012). According to a meta-analysis of studies performed by Erdt et al. (Erdt et al. 2016), the correlation with citations for Mendeley is 0.37 (ibid.: 1145). There are only low correlations with citations for the arts and humanities in all reference management software providers according to Sugimoto et al. (Sugimoto et al. forthcoming).

Recently, studies in the Altmetrics focused also on cross validations within Altmetrics and comparisons to bibliometric indicators. According to Erdt et al. (2016: 1145), correlation with other Altmetrics data sources are highest for CiteULike with a correlation of 0.32 (Li et al. 2012). Data reported by Gunn (2013) suggest that correlations are higher between Mendeley readings and downloads in PLoS than between Mendeley readings and citations. In a similar vein, the study revealed that recommendation on F1000Prime increases readings on Mendeley (Bornmann 2014b; Gunn 2013).

6.4. Empowering Reproducibility: Sharing Data and Code

Against governmental and societal appraisals, the assessment of sharing of data and code has still not flourished among the scientific communities. Consequently, only rare data are available and almost no metrics have been developed up to now (Konkiel 2013). Although first indicators are available (Costas et al. 2013), their diffusion is still low and so are studies in the informetric, bibliometric and scientometric community (Sugimoto et al. forthcoming). Consequently, increasing attention about that subject could be a contribution of this project (see also Annex 1).

6.5. Stabilizing Knowledge: Online Encyclopedias & Guidelines

As the section on data sources in Altmetrics has shown (section 5.1.), Online Encyclopaedias are increasingly receiving attention by scholars (Archambault et al. 2013; Black 2008; Bould et al. 2014; Hodis et al. 2008; Nielsen 2007a; PLOS ALM et al. 2014; Wilson and Likens 2015). In the life sciences, wikis are increasingly used and maintained to keep up with the increasing pace of knowledge production (Archambault et al. 2013; Callaway 2010). Wikipedia as the most important becomes a valuable and acknowledged source in the scientific community (Chesney 2006; Okoli et al. 2014; Rush and Tracy 2010). Scholars are, however, only rarely active in producing content in that source (Procter et al. 2013). Hence, the percentage of scientific papers by Wikipedia remains low: According to Alperin (Alperin 2014), the coverage is about 1%. As recent studies suggest, such low scholarly participation might indicate a deficit in the integration of Wikipedia in scientific reward systems: A study conducted by Samoilenko and Yasseri of 400 biographical entries in Wikipedia of four different fields has found no correlations between centrality in Wikipedia and citations (Samoilenko and Yasseri 2014). In a similar vein, a study by Haustein et al. revealed that many scholars do not believe that Wikipedia could be appropriate for evaluation purposes (Haustein, Peters, Bar-Ilan et al. 2014).

On the other side, content produced by Wikipedia entries is increasingly cited, though from a very low basis (PLOS ALM et al. 2014). According to Nielsen (Nielsen 2007b), there is a moderate correlation between mentions on Wikipedia and citations. Citations from the most reputed journals such as Science and Nature are overrepresented in Wikipedia (Nielsen 2007a).

6.6. Valuing and scrutinizing Altmetrics: What do we learn?

The sheer amount of these studies reported in chapters 5 & 6 and the attention they receive among the big Open Access journals reveals that Altmetrics appear to be an important topic in debates on scholarly communication among which scrutinizing studies seems to currently be most relevant. Such attention has been often related to the influence of online social media platforms who are increasingly shaping and restricting societal and scholarly life (Cambrosio et al. 2009; Gillespie 2010, 2015; Keating and

Cambrosio 2003). By providing not only means for social networking and sharing content, but also maintaining and controlling the technical infrastructures and channels for communication, platforms increasingly produce dependencies and create technical as well as societal power: 'Platforms intervene' (Gillespie 2015). Such dependencies can be also observed in the system of alternative scholarly communication and evaluation, which have been particularly shaped by the Altmetrics aggregators and their orchestration of data sources. Their selection and use of data sources surely contributes to what we have termed the acts of valuation of categorization in Altmetrics. As the review of scholarly literature in chapters 5 & 6 has shown, the dependencies on these platforms do not only influence the production and consumption of social media channels but also the execution of studies dedicated to Altmetrics (Gonzalez-Valiente et al. 2016).

Consequently, given the dependence on Almetrics providers and platforms, one theme, which came up in the existing literature on exploring sources and utilizations, is heterogeneity. The Altmetrics aggregators provide different data sources with different audiences, purposes, and metrics which are hence difficult to generalize (Bornmann and Haunschild 2016d; Zahedi et al. 2014; Zahedi, Z., Fenner, M., & Costas, R. 2015). This different provision of sources by Altmetrics aggregators and their utilizations by the wider scholarly audience indicates that no clear cut profile of the Altmetrics sources and their scholarly use can be provided. Currently, first reviews have come up that aim at providing a state of the art analysis for these developments. According to Sugimoto et al (Sugimoto et al. forthcoming), the heterogeneity of the platforms and the dependency of users to these platforms make some emerging indicators 'entirely specific' to these platforms. They interpret the vast development of Altmetrics providers and its usage and diffusion as convergence of interests from public stakeholders, such as policy (James Wilsdon et al. 2015) and society on the one side, and the interests of scholarly publishers on the other. By creating incentives and reward structures for any scholarly activity might lead to a gamification of research activities (ibid.). However, we still lack a clear understanding of the relations between Altmetrics, the motivations of their users, and their impact on the reward system of scholarly activities.

Based upon the insufficient description heterogeneity of sources and platforms, scholars in the reviewed literature have frequently criticized the confusing terminology of Altmetrics. This applies not only to the definition of the term Altmetrics itself (Haustein, Bowman, Costas 2016) but also more specifically to how Altmetrics aggregators as the main drivers of the movement term what qualifies an event in Altmetrics - such as being mentioned, cited, downloaded etc.- (Barthel et al. 2015; Liu and Adie 2013). This applies to Facebook counts in altmetric.com, but also to Mendeley readership or other events in the Altmetrics landscape (Haustein, Bowman, Costas 2016). These events are not only termed differently, but they also represent different performative acts that needed to be understood from a theoretical perspective in order to provide a systematic account for the users in libraries and public encyclopaedias.

Consequently, observers of the Altmetrics development are still critical as to how data are systematically collected, tracked, and finally measured. According to Erdt et al., the collection of data sources remains problematic since data collection demands time and object identifier such as DOI or title are not always consistently trackable. Closely related to data collection problems is the problem of disambiguation since the travelling of research objects across various differently coded sites (Erdt et al. 2016). These deficits cannot only perceived as problems of data integrity as Erdt et al. (2016: 1149) suggest. Instead, as we have proposed, it remains unclear whether Altmetrics measures can generally contribute complementary issues to the valuation acts in science and society. As some scholars indicate, Altmetrics provide an opportunity to reach new societal audiences, Altmetrics are perceived as an additional possibility to study research collaborations and academic networks complementing bibliometric co-authorship and co-citation analysis (Wouters and Costas 2012). According to Erdt et al. (2016:1149) interaction between humanities and computer science is needed to gain more information about the qualities of such collaboration practices and how they are shaped by technology (Taylor 2013).

Based upon increasing discontent about research into Altmetrics, scholars have turned to more fundamental and reflexive issues in the last two years. Although scrutinizing and validation topics are still most prevalent, new conceptualization efforts and new research perspectives have been put to the fore that seem to broaden the debate on Altmetrics. The literature on these topics is in such a way recent that it has even not been covered by the forthcoming reviews of Erdt et al., Sugimoto et al. and Gonzalez

& Valiente. Consequently, in the following chapter, we aim at providing insights in the landscape of steady and upcoming themes in Altmetrics.

7. Most recent debates in Altmetrics between 2015 and 2016

As shown in chapter 5 & 6 research into Altmetrics has gained a considerable amount of momentum in the recent years, which is probably also influenced by the dominance and visibility of Altmetrics providers but also by policy oriented literature (James Wilsdon et al. 2015) and increasing or first standardization attempts such as the whitepaper on Altmetrics by the National Information Standards Organization (NISO, 2014). The purpose of this chapter is to focus on some prevalent issues in the recent developments in the field of Altmetrics over the last two years. This view should not be understood as a complete assessment of all challenges, but as a specific focus on issues that govern current research. A more comprehensive list of issues, covering a broader perspective also including a forward-looking approach towards Altmetrics is provided at the end of this report. Among the most prevalent topics, methodological and conceptual issues seem to make up a considerable amount of recent works, an increased need of understanding Altmetrics through user motivations and in-depth content analyses,

the drift of altmetric approaches towards country level assessment, and most recent expansions of new data sources in Altmetrics.

7.1. Scrutinizations towards methods and data

The recent years in Altmetrics-related publications have been characterized by a surge of methodological scrutinizations towards Altmetrics (for a comprehensive overview see Erdt et al. 2016). Focusing on the most recent two years, this trend seems to be unbroken and will likely continue in the near future, especially with the increased integration of new sources of data under the umbrella term Altmetrics. A majority of approaches focused on correlations between citation counts and Altmetrics: Costas et al. (Costas et al. 2014), for instance, conducted a multidisciplinary overview, while Bar-Ilan et al. conducted a case study for the field astrophysics (Bar-Ilan 2014), Martinez & Anderson (2015) focused on an analysis of the International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning (Martinez and Anderson 2015), De Winter analyzed relationships between tweets and citations for articles in PLOS one (de Winter, 2015), and Sotudeh et al. analysed correlations for the field of Library and Information Science (Sotudeh et al. 2015). Other approaches focus on issues of data integrity in Altmetrics (Gordon et al. 2015; Zahedi, Z., Fenner, M., & Costas, R. 2015). Gorraiz and colleagues (Gorraiz et al. 2016) have assessed the availability and coverage of Digital Object Identifiers (DOI) for Web of Science and Scopus. Instead, fewer papers in the last two years have covered issues such as data integrity and coverage for research data (for instance Peters et al. 2016) and the specific problems of software mentioned in publications (Howison and Bullard in press).

One very specific theme that reached the attention of scholars in the Altmetrics community is normalization (Bornmann and Haunschild 2016b; Haunschild and Bornmann 2016).¹⁶ These issues have been part of most citation-based bibliometric indicators such as the Mean Citation Rate or the Field Normalized Citation Rate. From a methodological standpoint that also shows that the topic Altmetrics is still highly connected to “traditional indicators”. While the data sources and notions of impact connected to these indicators vary, the general principles are still in force. The issue of normalization also introduces challenges, mainly to answer the question: “Normalize to what exactly?” In bibliometric databases, the amount of documents that need to be taken into account to assess a standard of reference is rather controlled or reflects a “closed universe of scholarly communication”, which is reflected in the differentiation between source and non-source items (Butler and Visser 2006), i.e. documents that are part of the database and documents that are not part of the database. With the rise of Altmetrics, such an assessment of reference is more of a challenge. The “open universe of scholarly communication” does not easily allow for a formulation of a reference corpus, a challenge that has also been recognized in early cybermetrics studies (Bar-Ilan 1999; Rousseau 1997), as chapter 3 has shown. One challenge is that not all sources can be sufficiently captured and ordered through the same tape of classification scheme. Other challenges lie in assessing a “total amount of documents”, which is difficult, and in some cases may even be impossible to do. Further challenges for these activities are the volatility introduced by the dynamic nature of social media data sources and the World Wide Web in general.

Yet, normalization is relevant, especially for Altmetrics that aim to reach beyond the level of comparison amongst individuals and self-assessment. While on a bi-lateral level, comparisons can be achieved, comparisons towards entities such as “disciplines” or “fields” are not possible without normalization. One might argue that the increasing discourse on normalization reflects a professionalization of these indicators from the perspective of established scientometric research. Among the most prominent works towards normalization of Altmetrics are the efforts by Bornmann, Marx, and Haunschild for Mendely counts and twitter counts (Bornmann 2016b, Bornmann and Haunschild 2016a, 2016b, 2016c; Bornmann and Marx 2015) the works of Hausteine et al. (Hausteine, Costas et al. 2015; Hausteine, Larivière et al. 2014), Thelwall & Fairclough (Thelwall and Fairclough 2015) and Costas et al. (Costas et al. 2014).

¹⁶ Normalization is the procedure of relating metric counts to a standard of reference such as a mean of indicator values for a field or country, a sum of values in terms of a share or other measures. Other forms of normalization can be termed between indicator types, e.g. Gross Domestic Product Per Capita.

Solving challenges of normalization will have a high impact on the future opportunities for Altmetrics. First and foremost, the impact will increase the chance of applying Altmetrics for comparative analyses on a national or a regional level, but also on the level of comparative analyses between and within disciplines and fields.

7.2. The sustained need for conceptual scrutinizations in Altmetrics

The lack of a coherent theoretical and conceptual framework is a shortcoming that has been discussed increasingly in the two recent years. Even though there exist a number of mostly conflicting theories regarding citations inspired by numerous disciplines such as psychology, sociology, rhetoric, information theory or even physical metaphors, a holistic theory of citation has not been presented yet. Altmetrics suffer in a similar way from this problematic heritage (Bornmann 2016b). Some very recent attempts highlight the necessity of such theoretical underpinnings once more such as Haustein et al. (Haustein, Bowman, Costas 2016). With the increasing prominence of Altmetrics as a complementary set of indicators and new source of assessment, the recent years feature an increasing amount of papers that articulate criticism towards these conceptual deficits (Gumpenberger et al. 2016). That issues has been also highlighted by a whitepaper on Alternative Metrics published by the National Information Standards Organization (NISO, 2014). While in the previous years, we find mostly scrutinizations that are aimed at cross-indicator validations (Erdt et al. 2016), we find increasing criticism towards such often atomized studies. These type of discussions include both terminological issues as well as issues regarding the nature of impact that is deemed to be captured through Altmetrics (Bornmann 2014a, 2014b, 2016a; Calabuig et al. 2016; Cress 2014; Ferer 2016; Gutierrez et al. 2015). This shift in part reflects the re-emergence of argumentative patterns of the early phases of cybermetrics/webometrics research (Bossy 1995), see also chapter 3.

Most conceptual criticism towards Altmetrics in this regard is found in the role of what Altmetrics scores signify. A predominant issue is the interpretation of Altmetrics reflecting societal impact or scholarly quality. Some scholars argue that Altmetrics measure „attention“ rather than scholarly quality, importance or impact (Franzen 2015; Haustein, S., Bowman, T. D., & Costas, R. 2015; Kortelainen and Katvala 2012): "Altmetrics do not, and probably cannot, serve the certification function of scholarship, a function that establishes the validity of a research finding. Altmetrics measure attention, not the soundness of an article's data, methodologies, or findings." (Beall 2015: 2020). Against arguments of social media scholars who sometimes overrate the influence of social media in scholarly communication, Stefanie Haustein has put that more conceptual care is needed to grasp what kind of impact Altmetrics is producing: "In this context, it cannot be emphasized enough that social media activity does not equal social impact" (Haustein 2016b). Similar positions are held by Melero (2015), who concludes that an indicator of discussion does not necessarily signal social impact (Melero 2015). Yet, other types of Altmetrics, such as assessment of citations towards publications in specific types of documents that reach beyond intra-scientific discourse such as clinical guidelines (Thelwall and Maflahi 2016) or policy documents (Konkiel et al. 2016) are argued to hold the potential for assessment of societal impact.

Other scholars argue, that despite accepting a notion of attention being measured, such indicators for now do not reflect career-relevant forms of valuation. "Neither Twitter mentions nor Facebook 'likes' are, for now at any rate, accepted currencies in the academic marketplace; you are not going to get promoted for having been liked a lot." (Cronin 2013: 1523). While such an assessment will have to stand the test of time and further progress, it probably falls short to capture the signalling power such indicators may have in specific disciplines, regardless of what they actually do or do not measure. Regarding career-specific aspects, some scholars argue that an increased importance of Altmetrics might hold the threat of goal displacement, while at the same time there is a lack of to "understand the underlying mechanisms of measures of attention" (Sugimoto 2015). Similar arguments are put forward by Blackman (2016), who exclaims that Altmetrics are less aimed at modifying and empowering previously less appreciated forms of output, but rather reflect an increased automatization of the scholarly reward system (Blackman 2016). "In this sense, [Altmetrics] algorithms are part of a new micro-physics of power, which entangle material, psychological, cultural and historical processes as part

of their automated logics. These extend beyond and have the potential to govern and shape the actions of individual users." (Blackman 2016: 19).

A quite similar argument has been put forward by Moed (2016), who states, that "Altmetrics is more than measuring attention in social media to scientific-scholarly artefacts, but should be conceived as metrics of the computerization of the research process in general," (Moed 2016: 368). Some argue, that some activities on which Altmetrics indicators are based on reflect this new form of reception in an even more extreme way, and proclaim, that „most tweets to a given article probably arise from very little of the article being read“ (Moore 2016: 713). Others argue that Altmetrics, rather than organizing information overload, represents a new form of information overload: "The information ecosystem is too fragmented and heterogeneous to be explored as a whole, even at a disciplinary level, and we are now faced with too much data to be properly explored at a more granular level." (Stuart 2015: 853). Gumpenberger et al. (2016) even fear that the increased attention towards social-media related scholarly communication establishes the „tower of babel, where millions of scientists talk or write at the same time and produce billions of papers, talks, emails, blog entries, tweets, etc., to be evaluated, discussed, mentioned, commented, re-blogged, re-tweeted and scored by others. But at the end of the day, we might have lost a common understanding on what this is all about," (Gumpenberger et al. 2016: 918).

Some scholars, including most of the aforementioned in this chapter, argue for a shift in focus towards Altmetrics as a tool of understanding the practice of research, an argument reminiscent of the perspective by Bossy (1995) in the early years of cybermetrics. These scholars generally argue that Altmetrics should be interpreted as a means for uncovering previously hidden forms and mechanisms of scholarly work. For instance, a recent study finds that mentions in Twitter and Facebook correlate with the use of tags reflecting appropriateness for teaching in F1000 papers (Haustein, Sugimoto et al. 2015). Other scholars argue from a pragmatic perspective despite essential assumption towards the content itself and advocate for a forward-looking perspective that will resolve over time. „Thus, Altmetrics is still in its infancy stage in comparison to the decades old scientometric field and it will take much time to become a mature branch of study. However, the importance of Altmetrics cannot be overlooked in changing world of digital technology," (Dhiman 2015: 314). Enis (2015) perceives the developments less as a threat in terms of balanced evaluation, but rather as input to strategic self-marketing of scholars in the digital age focusing on the catalyst function of Altmetrics towards reputation (Enis 2015). He argues that in a way "as the field of Altmetrics enters the second half of the decade, its potential for reputation management and community building may be key areas for outreach and scholarly communications librarians to watch,"(ibid.). Integrative attempts towards Altmetrics and institutionalized forms of evaluation vouch for an even stronger focus on conceptual cross-pollination and general principles that Altmetrics indicators should abide to. Bornmann & Haunschild contend that quality criteria, specifically the Leiden Manifesto, should be a blueprint for further assessments based on Altmetrics (Bornmann and Haunschild 2016d). They argue that for assessments based on Altmetrics, a number of criteria are not specific to scientometric approaches, but are also relevant in the Altmetrics domain. Among these criteria are the focus on further normalization attempts, taking into account the research mission and agenda, use of open and transparent data, and methods that are open to both conceptual and methodological critique and improvement, avoiding misplaced notions of accuracy and complementarity between scientometric and Altmetrics indicators.

Other attempts aim at establishing a different way of structuring Altmetrics by assessing Altmetrics through different types of impact, such as the idea of „impact flavors“ (Weller 2015) or establishing a hierarchy of Altmetrics by their impacts (Holmberg 2015). Still, such attempts have not yet led to a viable form of vertical or horizontal structuration of Altmetrics indicators, a notion which also has been highlighted as a future issue by the NISO whitepaper (NISO, 2015). To assert and flesh out such concepts will be a vital ingredient to the promotion activities in WP5 of the OpenUp project. First and foremost, be establishing a taxonomical approach towards linking dissemination channels and impact.

Overall, we can conclude that in the recent years, the community is moving towards attempts to gain a better understanding of the conceptual level of Altmetrics. In general, we find two broader strains of approaches to reach this goal. First, we find an increase in attempts to understand Altmetrics through understanding the users and stakeholders of Altmetrics. Second, we find approaches that focus on

content-based approaches (Bornmann 2016b), focusing less on numeric nature of Altmetrics but rather seeking a deeper understanding through focusing on the messages and content by which new media is being put into action to invoke scholarly outputs and researchers.

7.3. Understanding Altmetrics through understanding users

In recent years, we find several articles discussing the role of users and user properties. Most studies focus on the use of microblogging or social media services, with studies focussing on differences between user groups (Barthel et al. 2015; Holmberg and Thelwall 2014; Ortega, J. 2015; Ortega, J. 2015a), or academic rank or age (Mansour 2015; Mohammadi and Thelwall 2014; Mohammadi et al. 2015; Mohammadi et al. 2016a; Zahedi and van Eck 2014; Zahedi, Z., Costas, R., & Wouters, P. 2015) or gender differences (Bar-Ilan 2014; Birkholz, J.M., Seeber, M., & Holmberg, K. 2015; Paul-Hus et al. 2015, Tsou et al. 2015, 2015). Some studies specifically highlight the importance of user motivations (Haustein, Bowman, Holmberg et al. 2016; Mohammadi et al. 2016a; Ringelhan et al. 2015; Tsou et al. 2015). In contrast to studies from previous years, these user-based validation studies imply that Altmetrics has started to move beyond the initial stages of cross-metric and cross-domain validation studies and honouring the diversity of impacts and the need to assess these in their own right. Also, these types of studies seem to be motivated by the previously discussed conceptual scrutinization attempts that aim at delimiting the impact of individual Altmetrics data and methods to one dimension of impacts, but rather towards a multi-dimensional and holistic understanding of the impacts captured through Altmetrics.

7.4. Understanding Altmetrics through Content Analysis

Another recent strand of research advocates the use of content analyses. In order to solve some conceptual problems regarding Altmetrics, it is argued, that the focus of analyses should also shift towards the meaning and the content that is both - produced and received - in the new channels of dissemination covered by Altmetrics. Analyzing health-related research blogs, Shema et al. (2015) developed a taxonomy of 10 categories that are typically reflect the topic of blog posts including “discussion” of a topic, “criticism” towards the topic reported, “advice” such as recommendations to blog readers, “trigger” reflecting a direct stimulus that led to writing a blog post, “extensions” suggesting further reading or lines of research, “self” related to blog posts about the blogger itself, “controversy”, and “other” (Shema et al. 2015). In a letter to the editor of the Journal of Scientometrics, Bornmann argues in a similar direction (Bornmann 2015). From his perspective, the cross-validation and correlative studies making up the majority of current validation attempts fall short of establishing the “meaning” behind these communicative acts. Exemplifying his argument by a conceptual analyses of the Twitter messages about the seminal paper that introduced the concept of the Hirsch Index (Hirsch 2005) he can conclude that without a stronger focus on the content of such communication acts the summative logic of Altmetrics cannot be warranted as a specific type of impact, but rather introduces a new source of confusion into informetric and scientometric analyses in general.

7.5. Moving Altmetrics to the regional and international level

One of the strengths Altmetrics are accounted for is the potential to provide timely information compared to indicators based on citations in peer-reviewed journals. For the latter, the time lag is a result of the inclusion cycles in bibliographic databases and more pronouncedly the period of time required to allow for a statistical sound differentiation emerging between articles. Citation windows, and thereby time lag to arrive at a sound assessment, can vary between 2 to 5 years. Furthermore, taking into account those studies that established positive correlations between Altmetrics and citation counts, an increased interest in the potential for country level assessments and informing science and innovation policy through Altmetrics is plausible.¹⁷

All in all, country level Altmetrics or Altmetrics relating to the specific limitations or opportunities of specific countries vis-à-vis Altmetrics is becoming increasingly relevant resulting in both studies that

¹⁷ According to Erdt et al. (2016) the overall highest positive levels of correlations between Altmetric scores and citations can be found for social bookmarking and reference managers Mendeley & CiteULike.

aim to establish the potential for international comparison but also country-level studies. The latter type of studies, the assessment of biases in favour or disfavour of a country in terms of the coverage and validity of specific indicators has a long-standing tradition in scientometrics. Especially in the context of validity of the former type of studies: metric-based country comparisons. Currently, studies of coverage focus on Spain (Gonzalez-Diaz et al. 2015), Latin America (Alperin 2015; Araujo, R. F., Murakami, T. R., De Lara, J. L., & Fausto, S. 2015), India (Kali 2015), South Africa (Onyanha 2015), United Kingdom (Birkholz, J.M., Seeber, M., & Holmberg, K. 2015), Iran (Maleki 2015a, 2015b), and on international comparative level. Genuine approaches towards country-level Altmetrics are yet rare to find with the three exceptions of Alhoori et al. (2014), Fairclough & Thelwall (2015), and Haunschild et al. (2015). Most likely, future potentials for country-level Altmetrics will be realized based on Mendeley data. Yet, future developments in the area of indicator normalization and conceptual assessment of new forms of impact for specific groups of Altmetrics indicators might shift attention towards other sources of data.

7.6. The ever-expanding universe of Altmetrics

One of the arguments put forward to promote Altmetrics, is to establish an environment of appreciation for diverse scientific outputs beyond the scope of “traditional” scientometric indicators focusing on peer-reviewed journal articles and its derivatives such as citations based on these data sources (Priem 2013; Priem et al. 2012). Another relevant aspect common to most concepts of Altmetrics is its demarcation to “traditional” indicators (Eysenbach 2011). This open formulation allows both for openness in Altmetrics coverage of different types of impacts and also in an open concept towards new sources of data that is further promoted through the notion of polymorphous appraisal (Cronin et al., 1998). From a conceptual standpoint, there seems to be no ex-ante limit to the inclusion of new sources of data; although the challenge resides on the conceptual level to assess nature and type of the latent concept that in consequence is the basis of the impact proclaimed. Despite overall compendia of sources of impact in light of evaluation (e.g. Wouters and Costas 2012), and overviews, such as those developed within the EC-funded ACUMEN project (Kousha and Thelwall 2015b, Thelwall and Kousha 2015b, 2015d), some specific types of activities seem to gather increased attention within the Altmetrics community. Among the sources that gather an increased focus of attention are books (Kousha and Thelwall 2015a) as well as metrics based on data from Academic Social Networks such as Research Gate or Academia.edu (Hoffmann et al. 2016b; Thelwall and Kousha 2014).

Current citation indices for books are comparably small with Thomsons Book Citation Index covering ca. 75.000 books and Scopus covering around 30.000 books. Yet, addressing data source such as book reviews or analyses based on Google Books can be relevant sources of output indicators, especially in the Social Sciences & Humanities. At this time, the best overview regarding the assessment of Altmetrics-based assessment of books can be found in Kousha & Thelwall (Kousha and Thelwall 2015a). According to this article, a number of different types of methods can be used to assess the impact of books: Citations in Google Books (e.g. Kousha & Thelwall, 2014), usage and purchasing statistics of libraries (Torres-Salinas et al. 2013), scholarly and non-scholarly online book reviews as well as sentiment analyses of such reviews (Kousha and Thelwall 2015a, 2016; Zhou et al. 2015; Zhou, Q., & Zhang, C. 2015; Zuccala et al. 2015), Mendeley bookmarks to books (Mohammadi et al. 2016a) and mentions in academic syllabi (Hammarfelt 2014; Kousha and Thelwall in press).

Social networking sites such as Facebook and Google+ have been in the corpus of social media-related Altmetrics for a substantial amount of time (see chapter 5). In the two recent years, there seems to be a trend in the Altmetrics community to broaden the focus on Academic Social Networks such as Academia.edu or ResearchGate (Thelwall and Kousha 2014, 2015a). With their specific role between formal and informal scholarly communication, such specific social networking sites do away with “some” of the conceptual problems and limitations of generic social networking site analysis, albeit shifting the focus back towards a more closed universe approach, as has been common in scientometrics (Jordan 2014). The analysis of data generated by academic social networking sites can yield some interesting insights into the structure (Mansour 2015) and dynamics of science (Megwalu 2015), alternative measures for distribution of social and reputational capital (Thelwall et al. 2016), but also in terms of scholarly “activity indicators” (Yu et al. 2016) by communication and support processes (Jeng et al. 2015), e.g. answering questions in Q&A forums or acts of appraisal and endorsement of scholars

and their respective self-categorization into academic topics. Also, such academic sites might in the future be interesting in terms of analyzing their potential for hiring and job search through ties within these networks. Yet, how these types of data source may reflect broader impact categories is yet unclear (Thelwall and Kousha 2015a). Also, there seem to exist disciplinary differences in preference towards the major platforms (Ortega 2015; Ortega 2015), posing additional challenges towards cross-disciplinary assessments.

Using ResearchGate Scores as means of evaluation is yet a matter of dispute within the community (Jordan 2015; Kraker and Lex 2015). While some appreciate the potential of these metrics (Nicholas et al. 2016; Nicholas et al. 2014), Kraker & Lex (2015) devise some caution and limitations of these scores, such as its lack of transparency of calculation, its reliance on the disputed Journal Impact Factor, and volatility in how the indicator is calculated (Kraker and Lex 2015). Jordan (2015) argues, however, that some of these shortcomings may be solved through reverse-engineering the composition of the RG Score (Jordan 2015).

7.7. Summary of recent issues

These issues indicate that Altmetrics scholarship has reached a certain stage of stabilization. What we have witnessed in the past few years is not only an elaboration on methodological issues – such as advanced methods for validation and scrutinization, new research strategies – such as national and transnational approaches towards Altmetrics, new empirical phenomena such as ResearchGate, but also new, merely fundamental perspectives that allow for reflecting terminologies, methodologies and establishing new conceptualizations. User motivations are specifically acknowledged to understand the specificities and characteristics of each channel. For that purpose, quantitative macro analyses should be combined with content analysis in which attributed interpretations come to the fore. Increasingly, it appears, new phenomena (such as social networking sites, research blogs, and social recommending platforms are not only analyzed as an additional tool for research evaluation but as a channel of communication in itself that is infused with meaning and to which specific value is attributed (see chapter 5). It deems that these issues and the interest they raise among various communities could also offer the chance contributing to the theoretical and conceptual development in scientometric and informetric studies of scholarly communication in general. Still, however, there are also a number of problems and threats that the field faces, partly exactly because the field receives a lot of attention, which should be dealt with in more detail. For this reason, the last chapter provides an in depth analysis of strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats, which takes up all the issues that have been provided in this report.

8. Assessment of the current field of Altmetrics

The purpose of this chapter is to provide an initial assessment of the current state of Altmetrics based on the overall literature collected to compile this report. This should be seen as a preliminary set of issues that can for now not be deemed a complete list. This initial assessment will act as a starting point for further a community-based assessment of issues around Altmetrics and will be gradually extended and refined over the course of the OpenUp project through the input of practitioners and experiences from the pilot case studies conducted in the second phase of the project.

8.1. Strengths of Altmetrics

Timeliness of some metrics

Timeliness of Altmetrics compared to other types of established indicators of research output or reception via citation to peer-reviewed journals is one major strength. Yet, the argument of timeliness has to be carefully considered for each of the Altmetrics data sources rather than for the umbrella term “Altmetrics” as such. While fast-paced social media, microblogging and social reference management might provide more timely data, an assessment based on other indicators such as multimedia content,

syllabi references etc. might still produce considerable time lags. Also, eventual transformation time from one medium to the other has to be taken into account.

Complementary information filters

Alternative metrics provide complementary filters for information gathering and retrieval. The filtering will work best in cases where the actual use of dissemination channels captured by Altmetrics reached a substantial disciplinary or thematically oriented diffusion within a community.

Catalyst function towards downstream impacts

Even though the actual type and extent of impact for different types of alternative metrics is actually not currently resolved, there seems to be plausible arguments for a catalyst function of engagement with underlying dissemination channels towards wider forms of impact. This might not apply in the same way to all data sources covered by alternative metrics, but engagement via some channels might eventually be valuation acts in themselves. While this is not directly a strength of quantification itself, the option of signaling a certain providence for certain individual Altmetrics dimensions can act as an incentive to engage in these types of activities. The ultimate merit therefore has to be captured in the act itself.

Responsiveness through open concept

The openness of the concept of alternative metrics can be interpreted as a strength as well as a weakness. The strength of conceptual openness, especially towards integration of new forms of dissemination as basis of assessment, can enable overall responsiveness to changes within evaluation logics or changes in establishing reward systems or incentive schemes. Yet, integration of new forms of sources should be guided by careful reason of what may be plausibly reflect extended or new forms of valuation.

Balanced signaling of importance and impact

Enabling researchers to diverge their signalling, e.g. by highlighting some previously hidden benefits of their work, e.g. integration in teaching curricula, clinical guidelines or policy documents, has led to a positive assessment by parts of the scientific community, especially by some early-career scholars. Alternative metrics, albeit they might not have the effect of modifying selection mechanisms or be an integral or dominant element of career-promoting, allow researchers to differentiate and paint a more balanced picture.

Promotion of unique IDs

A substantial amount of current alternative metrics rely on the use of Digital Object Identifiers (DOI). While such a connection between metric and a specific requirement towards the use of specific communication symbols may lead to skewed results or problems in validity of indicators, it also promotes the use of such identifiers. This in itself can be argued to be a positive outcome in the long run, as it helps to organize and understand the stock of knowledge in a better way. Similar arguments can and have been made for other types of unique identifiers such as author IDs.

8.2. Weaknesses of Altmetrics

Data Integrity & Quality

One current issue that has been highlighted by many scholars is data integrity & quality. While in the “closed universe” of bibliometric source items of citing and inter-linkage can be clearly demarcated and more or less stable, the “open universe” approach of a considerable amount of Altmetrics data sources are potentially fluctuant. In a strict understanding Altmetrics may always change, depending on retrospective changes, e.g. deletion or modification, of the underlying data sources. Such volatilities also post a challenge to promotion and dissemination of these indicators on the level of certain stakeholder such as librarians. A second aspect of this issue are differences between data aggregators, due to

differences in data targeting, retrieval and processing strategies or which events are actually recorded, e.g. inclusion or exclusion of re-sharing messages or social media posts.

Confusion through Composite Indicators

The conflation of different forms of novel dissemination into a single numeric value may at first sight provide an easier mode of evaluation. Yet, at the same time such composite indicators have the weakness of potentially making an interpretation of this indicator harder in terms of evaluating its changes and extent of importance of the individual dimensions involved in the construction of it. This problem extends beyond the selection of dimensions and inputs into the weighting and re-scaling of individual data sources and dimensions. In the most extreme case, individual data sources, due to an inherent nature of the underlying dissemination channel, might overly influence the composite indicator outcome. For the case of Altmetrics the extent of the problem is further increased by the mutual entanglement of dissemination channels and data sources. This also highlights the need for further classification, providing taxonomies of orders of valuation for the different data sources.

Conceptual and terminological confusion

Even though we find an increased activity by researchers to gather further understanding of the underlying logics of individual data sources or differentiate between different types of actions or reactions that are being counted, there still is a lack of understanding in which way acts of valuation and evaluation are connected, i.e. how value generation and value appreciation are being matched in different dissemination channels. This is an issue that goes beyond simple problems of data specification, but rather touches on the disconnect between the importance within some media and their respective counting schemes.

Gaming

While the forging and colusionary modification of citation counts required either self-citations or acts of behavior modification of third parties, the new forms of referencing through social media are prone to new levels of manipulation reminiscent to the effects of link farms or search engine optimization and their impact on web page ranking. Manipulation no longer requires to modify the behaviour of others, but rather can be achieved by specialized programs and faked user accounts. Solving the problem by simple fraud detection algorithms neglect the conceptual decisions being implicit in such fraud detection. A social media account operated by a research organization or publisher exhibiting an increased amounts of posting and sharing activity might be deemed as legitimate outlet or illegitimate activity, depending on what kind of reasoning is applied to it.

Lack of research into Altmetrics on data, software and video content

While some data sources such as Mendeley or Twitter have attracted a considerable amount of activity, there are some domains of data sources that received very little attention, yet. Among those under-researched data sources are video content, research data, code and software. It seems, that most aspects relating to quality of these channels of dissemination have a metadata type of quality, i.e. they are properties of the output and are rather not linked to quantifiable metrics in the sense of Altmetrics. Yet, establishing such cross-validation between properties of these types of outputs could help to improve the understanding how and under which circumstances such properties of quality or openness relate to impact.

8.3. Opportunities linked to Altmetrics

New theoretical perspectives on impact

There have been recurring phases of criticism towards scientometrics about the low level of a coherent theoretical framing. With the uptake of alternative metrics this discussion has been reviewed and might also allow for the integration of new perspectives such as media theory. Moreover, the broadened focus might lead to theoretical frameworks which extent the realm of scientometrics and aims for a broader

theory of scientific regard including differentiated views both on the duality of production and reception of knowledge.

New ways of understanding the dynamics of science

The recent uptake of content-based analysis techniques might hold the opportunity for studies that allow for a better understanding of some aspects of dynamics of science, especially those that are related to the mutual dependencies of science and the public. In a similar vein, but focused more on the supply side of knowledge production, this might also be expected from user-motivation studies towards complementary forms of output beyond journal publications. Yet, such studies would probably have the highest impact if embedded in larger contexts of mixed method approaches integrating quantitative and qualitative aspects. Yet, the idea of user motivation studies and content-based analyses is not entirely a new phenomenon in scientometrics, but rather present standard techniques. The merit in this case will lie in the combination of assessing new forms of dissemination with these techniques and thereby a wider focus on the issues of science dynamics in general.

Potential for new cultures of appreciation

All forms of quantification are embedded in a wider context of ascription of meaning and actions. This also includes the relationship between classifications and valuations. With the rise of alternative metrics it is likely that new forms of classifications may arise that are linked to the legitimacy of the different latent concepts captured in these indicators but also in new forms of appreciation. The relationship between these individual aspects, i.e. appreciation of certain actions and traits, their quantification and their selective and the acts of establishing and applying classifications is unclear and will likely require dedicated research. Most likely such research will be on a disciplinary level at first. Understanding these interactions might allow for a clearer message what, why and how certain alternative metrics capture new and relevant forms of regard and how these feed back into cultures of selection and appreciation.

Increased speed of knowledge turnover

As one of the main strengths of alternative metrics is the timeliness in quantification of the output in different data sources and they represent complementary information filters it is also likely that alternative metrics could lead to an increased speed in knowledge turnover for a certain portion of research output. While this is a plausible outcome, it also is connected to a series of limitations. First, the timeliness is a function of the inherent mechanics of the medium and media use. In consequence, some media are more responsive and faster in stacking up indicator counts. If knowledge turnover is increased, it will likely be based on such media. Even though this is an overall positive outcome, it is also linked to the threat of algorithmization of knowledge turnover.

New ways of engaging and improving as a researcher

This potential is not linked to the numeric nature of alternative metrics, but rather the effect of screening and aggregating data and providing access to it. Most alternative metrics providers allow for an in-depth look into the data that make up the Altmetrics scores. Access to this underlying data can help researchers to assess the reception of their work, which in turn may support their scholarly development. Potential for improvement might range from passive approaches, e.g. qualitatively screening social media messages in which the research output is mentioned, to active approaches by engaging with the social media users directly. Yet, the positive impact of such will be influenced by the diversity of opinions and viewpoints on the reception side.

Motivations for improving data access and quality

The increased attention towards Altmetrics could have a positive impact on data provider motives to increase or modify data coverage and quality as well as improved functionality for Altmetrics analyses. While such developments will require time we can observe similar developments in the field of scientometrics and bibliographic data providers.

8.4. Threats linked to Altmetrics

Algorithmization of reception and knowledge flows

Algorithmization of reception behaviour has been a recurring motive in critique towards web-based or bibliometrically informed knowledge sourcing. The overall argument in all these critiques is the delegation and substitution of manual knowledge sourcing towards algorithmically informed knowledge sourcing will lead to a uniformity of knowledge sourcing and lock-in effects, which in turn will spur herding behaviour towards certain knowledge sources. Opponents to this view highlight that without such algorithmization the accelerating growth of new knowledge cannot be adequately addressed.

Strong dependence of Altmetrics on Digital Object Identifiers

One threat to Altmetrics is the strong dependence on DOIs. The problem in this case is twofold. First, research output that does not feature a DOI will potentially be covered less than research output that is covered by DOI. Second, variation in knowledge about the relevance of DOIs for Altmetrics could introduce a source of error both between but also within disciplines. This effect could be mediated both through the producer and user side of knowledge. Producers failing to include DOI information in their social media based communication could be at a loss of reception through not being covered by data collection through Altmetrics aggregators. Conversely, when the use of DOI is not widely diffused this might lead to bias in data from the reception side.

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Annex 1: Potential for software quality metrics as alternative metric indicators

Today, a number of competing frameworks for assessing software quality exist. Most of these frameworks are geared as guidance to allow a rational basis for selection of software, evaluation of development processes and as a general guideline to comparability. Currently, alternative metrics do not cover issues that relate to quality of either code or research data. One explanation for a lack of such information is the inherent logic of Altmetrics indicators, which are mainly aimed at capturing events related to research outputs rather than properties of the research output that are beyond necessary metadata to connect these events to the research objects. In the following we will discuss some approaches to assess open source quality and their potentials for Altmetrics indicators. This does not include mostly approaches that are inherent in an organizations software development and capture process characteristics such as data in an organization to uphold quality such as Total Quality Management (TQM).

An accepted approach to Software quality has been reflected in two formal standards by ISO/IEC 9126-X series up to 2011 and in the ISO/IEC 250XX Systems and software Quality Requirements and Evaluation (SQuaRE) from 2011 up to now harmonizing ISO/IEC 9126 series with ISO/IEC 14598. The goal of these standards is to set out a coherent terminology, taxonomy and measurement standards that can be applied to measure software and system quality in conjunction with the environment it is being used in as well as overall contexts including technical and non-technical aspects.

The overall quality model in these standards is divided into two parts. The “Quality in Use” model relates to the actual usage of the software. The “Product Quality” model relates to the product as such. The “Quality in Use” covers five characteristics towards the use of software complemented and enriched by several sub-characteristics (see Table 2) The “Product Quality” model consists of eight characteristics that can be assess without the software or system being in operation in a customer scenario (see Table 3). Such characteristics can be evaluated e.g. in testbeds or interview settings.

Table 2: Quality in use characteristics and sub-characteristics in the ISO/IEC 250XX series

Characteristic	Sub-characteristic	Explanation of Characteristic
Effectiveness		Accuracy and completeness with which users achieve specified goals
Efficiency		Resources expended in relation to the accuracy and completeness with which users achieve goals
Satisfaction	Usefulness Trust Pleasure Comfort	Degree to which user needs are satisfied when a product or system is used in a specified context of use
Freedom of risk	Economic risks Health & safety risks Environmental risks	Degree to which a product or system mitigates the potential risk
Context Coverage	Context completeness Flexibility	Degree to which a product or system can be used with effectiveness, efficiency, freedom from risk and satisfaction in all the specified contexts of use

Source: ISO/IEC 25010:2011

For each of these dimensions can be represented by a number of metrics which are chosen taking into account characteristics of the specific software, component or system in mind, e.g. economic sector, type of software and domain etc., and should always be selected in order to be supportive of the overall evaluation process and the needs of the evaluating organisation of individual. These are listed in ISO/IEC 2502X. There are tendencies for specific data collection methods. For instance, usability evaluation is usually performed by questionnaires, observing user behaviour or conducting user interviews, while reliability metrics usually rely on tracking faults in operation relative to overall product size or shares such as resolved faults relative to total amount of faults known.

Table 3: Product quality characteristics and sub-characteristics in the ISO/IEC 250XX series

Characteristic	Sub-characteristic	Explanation of Characteristic
Functional Suitability	Functional Completeness Functional Correctness Functional Appropriateness	Degree to which a product or system provides functions that meet stated and implied needs
Performance Efficiency	Time Behaviour Resource Utilization Capacity	Performance relative to the amount of resources
Compatibility	Co-existence Interoperability	Degree to which information can be exchanged with other entities
Usability	Appropriateness Recognizability Learnability Operability User Error Protection User Interface Aesthetics Accessibility	Degree to which a product or system can be used
Reliability	Maturity Availability Fault Tolerance Recoverability	Degree to which a system, product or component performs specified functions
Security	Confidentiality Integrity Non-Reputation Accountability	Degree to which a product or system protects information and data

	Authenticity	
Maintainability	Modularity Reusability Analysability Modifiability Testability	Degree of effectiveness and efficiency with which a product or system can be modified
Portability	Adaptability Installability Replicability	Degree of effectiveness and efficiency with which a system, product or component can be transferred

Source: ISO/IEC 25010:2011

All in all, the ISO/IEC 2500X series covers a substantial amount of potential metrics to use for evaluation. It presents a well-designed framework, which can be applied in multiple contexts and use cases. Yet, full-fledged quality assessment based on these standards presents a considerable amount of effort, which might not be in the scope and resource of a typical open source project. In order to address this, we screened approaches that are specifically aimed towards being applied in the Open Source context. We based our collection on currently available and wide spread open source quality models, screening each of the methods listed in this review for applicability. We found, that most open source quality models available today are exclusively based on ad-hoc assessments per product (Alfonzo et al. 2008; Atos 2006; Duijnhouwer F 2003; Petrinja et al.; Sung et al. 2007). Other approaches were excluded from further assessment, as they are highly domain specific (e.g. Müller, 2011; Cavus, 2011; Sohn et al., 2015). While domain-specificity should generally be assessed as a positive characteristic, since such approaches can be directly related to functionalities or specific requirements, they present a challenge for generating data that might be suitable for Altmetrics, as such approaches would need to be valid and applicable to all possible domains at the cost of less specificity. Finally, we only retained such approaches for further assessment that are based on at least some level of automatic or semi-automatic data collection methods. In total we find that only a very small fraction of open source quality assessment methods meet these criteria. These are the SQO-OSS approach, the EFFORT approach and some metrics that can be based on the technologies developed in the EC-funded OSSmeter project. The latter could be used to collect data as described in the individual assessments of the two approaches.

Based on the findings of the SQO-OSS project, Samoladas et al. (Samoladas et al. 2008) developed a set of metrics that in part might be used to assess such aspects of quality on a larger scale. In contrast to other approaches, the advantage of SQO-OSS is that its approach is mainly metric oriented with very low levels of intervention, a high degree of automatability of data collection and a focus on objective metrics rather than subjective metrics that need to be assessed on a per product basis. Their assessment is linked to the categories of the ISO/IEC 9126 Quality Model¹⁸. It is based on 10 attributes of metrics. These categories are “Analyzability”, “Changeability”, “Stability”, “Testability”, “Maturity”, “Effectiveness”, “Security”, “Mailing List”, “Documentation” and “Developer base”. For five of these categories, i.e. Analyzability, Changeability, Stability, Testability and Security, metrics can only be collected and assessed in terms of code audits and are therefore not directly suitable to collection in terms of Altmetrics approaches, mostly due to the lack of overall data sources that collect and offer access to such audit results.

Table 4: Selection of Attributes and metrics of the SQO-OSS Quality Model

Attribute	Metric
Analyzability	Comments frequency
Maturity	Number of open critical bugs in the last six months Number of open bugs in the last six months
Effectiveness	Number of critical bugs fixed in the last six months Number of bugs fixed in the last six months
Mailing list	Number of unique subscribers Number of messages in user/support list per month Number of messages in developers list per month Average thread depth
Documentation	Available documentation documents

	Update frequency
Developer base	Rate of developer intake Rate of developer turnover Growth in active developers

Source: Samoladas et al. (2008) adapted.

The second approach that might present some potentials for Altmetrics is The Evaluation Framework for Free/Open source projects (EFFORT) approach introduced by Aversano & Tortorella (Aversano and Tortorella 2011). Like the SQO-OSS quality model, EFFORT is oriented towards the now defunct ISO/IEC 9126-X series. It represent a mixed collection scheme covering different aspect of software quality in the three main categories which are again divided in sub-categories (see Table 5)

Table 5: Selection of Categories and Sub-Categories in the EFFORT Quality Model

Category	Sub-Category
Software Product Quality	Portability Maintainability Reliability Functionality Usability Efficiency
Community Trustworthiness	Developers Community Activity Support Tools Support Services Documentation
Product Attractiveness	Functional Adequacy Diffusion Cost effectiviess Legal reusability

Source: Aversano & Tortorella (2010).

The data collection process differs for each of the dimensions, ranging from user experience metrics towards automated and semi-automated collection methods. While assessment of the first category is exclusively based on a questionnaire assessment the categories “community trustworthiness” and “product attractiveness” are in part based on metrics that could eventually be generated applying advanced Natural Language Processing (NLP) techniques to project-specific web resources or analysis of data readily available within repositories.

Table 6: Selection of Sub-categories and metrics of the EFFORT Quality Model

Sub-Category	Metric	Source
Portability	Number of operating systems supported Availability of Installation Manual	Documentation, Project Website Documentation, Project Website
Developers	Number of Committers	Repository
Community Activity	Number of major releases per year Average number of commits per year Average number of commits per committer Closed Bugs Index	Repository Repository Repository Repository
Support Tools	Average number of threads per year Index of unanswered threads Number of forums Average number of threads per forum Average number of posts per year Forum internationalisation level Number of trackers Volume of wikis Number of FAQs	Project forum Project forum Project forum Project forum Project forum Project forum Project forum Project wiki Project web site
Support Services	Availability of training services Temporal coverage of training services Availability of e-learning services Availability of phone assistance	Project web site Project web site Project web site Project web site

	Availability of certification services Availability of outsourcing services Availability of maintenance services Availability of services for TCO estimation Availability of consulting services	Project web site Project web site Project web site Project web site Project web site
Documentation	Number of topics in administrator documentation Number of topics in user documentation Number of topics technical documentation Number of topics in the other documents Number of additional documentation files	Project wiki Documentation Documentation Project wiki Repository and wiki
Diffusion	Number of downloads Repository popularity index Number of repository forge users Positive rating index Search Engine visibility Number of published books Number of citations by domain experts Number of academic publications	Repository Repository Repository Repository Search Engine Online sales platform search Bibliographic Database Bibliographic Database

Source: Aversano & Tortorella (2013).

The advantage of most of the proposed metrics in this chapter is that they are both inherently varying over time, i.e. they change over time, and that they can be used to assess the underlying dynamic of open source. Yet, the respective metrics would have to be interpreted with caution. First, some of the metrics are inherently confounded with updates of the code. The more updates and features embedded in software, i.e. the more new code is introduced, the higher the likelihood of bugs introduced. This implies that projects that are increasing their scope might be penalized by such activities. Second, due to the sequential mode of innovation in software development and the high level of sharing, inclusion and modularization of code the attribute of bugs is hard to measure without bias. To reduce this bias, in-depth assessment of bugs would be required. If an open source project features dependencies to other pieces of code this can lead to a cascading effect if bugs are discovered within these dependencies. Common practice in open source software development is to flag such bugs as upstream to the dependencies. Still, these would register as bugs even though there are not directly under the responsibility of the project as such. Third, the direction of the metrics in terms of the assessment of positive or negative aspects of quality are unclear. A high number of bugs can be the result of problems within the code itself, but could also be a sign of a vibrant and engaged user base. Code or software that is rarely used will lack such clearing capacity. In consequence, vibrant projects might be penalized if the notion of “the less bugs, the better” is applied to the metric. Similar is true in part for metrics related to mailing lists with a similar line of reasoning. Mailing list activity can be moderated by interest in the software, but also be positive correlated to the number of bugs. Moreover, such metrics have to be considered in terms of the overall relationship between factors of the software project and impact on the individual characteristics. As Ahmed et al. (2014) found code quality of open source project tends to decrease with age and size of a project unless the growth is reflected in an increased developer group (Ahmed et al. 2014). Yet, with increasing number of core developers higher-level design of the code also decreases (Ahmed et al.2014).